

Polarity-guided uneven mitotic divisions control brassinosteroid activity in proliferating plant root cells

Graphical abstract

Authors

Nemanja Vukašinić, Che-Wei Hsu, Marco Marconi, ..., Krzysztof Wabnik, Trevor M. Nolan, Eugenia Russinova

Correspondence

nolan@caltech.edu (T.M.N.),
eugenia.russinova@psb.vib-ugent.be (E.R.)

In brief

Single-cell transcriptomics and live-cell imaging reveal brassinosteroid fluctuations across the cell cycle in plant roots. Uneven brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis in newly formed daughter cells ensure optimal root growth.

Highlights

- Brassinosteroid activity fluctuates across the cell cycle, peaking during the G1 phase
- Polarity-guided mitotic divisions establish differential signaling in daughter cells
- One daughter cell supports signaling, while the other enhances hormone biosynthesis
- Uneven brassinosteroid circumvents feedback loops, thus enhancing meristem activity

Article

Polarity-guided uneven mitotic divisions control brassinosteroid activity in proliferating plant root cells

Nemanja Vukašinović,^{1,2,17} Che-Wei Hsu,^{3,4,5,17} Marco Marconi,⁶ Shaopeng Li,⁷ Christopher Zachary,^{1,2} Rachel Shahan,^{3,4,8} Pablo Szekley,^{3,4} Ziv Aardening,⁹ Isabelle Vanhoutte,^{1,2} Qian Ma,^{1,2} Lucrezia Pinto,^{1,2} Pavel Krupař,^{10,11} Nathan German,^{1,2} Jingyuan Zhang,³ Claire Simon-Vezo,^{1,2} Jessica Perez-Sancho,¹² Pepe Cana Quijada,¹² Qianzi Zhou,³ Laura R. Lee,¹³ Jianghua Cai,¹⁴ Emmanuelle M. Bayer,¹² Matyáš Fendrych,^{10,11} Elisabeth Truernit,¹⁵ Yu Zhou,⁷ Sigal Savaldi-Goldstein,⁹ Krzysztof Wabnick,^{6,16} Trevor M. Nolan,^{3,4,5,*} and Eugenia Russinova^{1,2,18,*}

¹Department of Plant Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Ghent University, Ghent 9052, Belgium

²Center for Plant Systems Biology, VIB, Ghent 9052, Belgium

³Department of Biology, Duke University, Durham, NC, USA

⁴Howard Hughes Medical Institute, Duke University, Durham, NC, USA

⁵Division of Biology and Biological Engineering, California Institute of Technology, 1200 East California Boulevard, Pasadena, CA 91125, USA

⁶Centro de Biotecnología y Genómica de Plantas (CBGP, UPM-INIA) Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) - Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA, CSIC), Campus de Montegancedo, Pozuelo de Alarcón, Madrid 28223, Spain

⁷College of Life Sciences, TaiKang Center for Life and Medical Sciences, Wuhan University, Wuhan 430072, China

⁸Department of Molecular, Cell and Developmental Biology, University of California, Los Angeles, Los Angeles, CA 90095, USA

⁹Faculty of Biology, Technion-Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa 3200003, Israel

¹⁰Department of Experimental Plant Biology, Charles University, Prague 12844, Czech Republic

¹¹Institute of Experimental Botany of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague 16502, Czech Republic

¹²Laboratoire de Biogenèse Membranaire, UMR5200, CNRS, Université de Bordeaux, Villenave d'Ornon, France

¹³Center for Genomics and Systems Biology, Department of Biology, New York University, New York, NY 10003, USA

¹⁴Key Laboratory of Plant Hormone Regulation and Molecular Breeding of Chongqing, School of Life Sciences, Chongqing University, Chongqing, China

¹⁵Institute of Molecular Plant Biology, Department of Biology, ETH Zurich, Zurich 8092, Switzerland

¹⁶Departamento de Biotecnología-Biología Vegetal, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Agronómica, Alimentaria y de Biosistemas, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid 28040, Spain

¹⁷These authors contributed equally

¹⁸Lead contact

*Correspondence: nolan@caltech.edu (T.M.N.), eugenia.russinova@psb.vib-ugent.be (E.R.)

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SUMMARY

Brassinosteroid hormones are positive regulators of plant organ growth, yet their function in proliferating tissues remains unclear. Here, through integrating single-cell RNA sequencing with long-term live-cell imaging of the *Arabidopsis* root, we reveal that brassinosteroid activity fluctuates throughout the cell cycle, decreasing during mitotic divisions and increasing during the G1 phase. The post-mitotic recovery of brassinosteroid activity is driven by the intrinsic polarity of the mother cell, resulting in one daughter cell with enhanced brassinosteroid signaling, while the other supports brassinosteroid biosynthesis. The coexistence of these distinct daughter cell states during the G1 phase circumvents a negative feedback loop to facilitate brassinosteroid production while signaling increases. Our findings uncover polarity-guided, uneven mitotic divisions in the meristem, which control brassinosteroid hormone activity to ensure optimal root growth.

INTRODUCTION

Plants can grow indefinitely. Continuous root growth is sustained by the root apical meristem. Stem cells in the meristem give rise to transit-amplifying cells, which undergo stereotypical divisions before expanding and differentiating into the mature root.^{1,2} Endogenous signals, including hormones, regulate cell divisions

within the meristem. The plant steroidal hormones, brassinosteroids, profoundly affect cell proliferation and elongation.^{3–5} In *Arabidopsis thaliana* (*Arabidopsis*) roots, optimal brassinosteroid levels are maintained through a transcriptional negative feedback loop, where increased signaling reduces hormone biosynthesis.^{6,7} Hormone levels exhibit a gradient along the root axis, peaking in the elongation zone to promote cell cycle exit and

Figure 1. Fluctuations of brassinosteroid-regulated genes over the course of the cell cycle revealed by scRNA-seq

(A) Four phases of the cell cycle and subphases of mitosis.

(B) A schematic depiction of scRNA-seq analysis of the cell cycle in *Arabidopsis* roots.

(C) Uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) representation of the proliferation domain and proximal root cap cells. Colors indicate cell cycle progression (see STAR Methods).

(D) Heatmap showing gene expression patterns over cell cycle pseudotime in proliferation domain atrichoblasts. Marker genes for each phase are indicated.

(E) Gene modules (Mod) identified from the clustering of proliferation domain atrichoblasts and their correlation with cell cycle progression.

(F) Gene expression patterns for each module are shown in (E).

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cell elongation.^{4,6} However, the role of brassinosteroids in proliferating cells is unclear. In the root meristem, low but sufficient brassinosteroid levels are crucial for normal root growth.⁶ Reduced brassinosteroid activity in biosynthetic and receptor mutants leads to decreased cell division, while exogenous brassinosteroids promote cell cycle exit, resulting in fewer divisions in the root meristems.^{3,5,6} The mechanisms for maintaining optimal brassinosteroid signaling and its variations during the cell cycle remain unknown.

Using single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) and long-term live-cell imaging, we show that brassinosteroid activity fluctuates during the cell cycle in dividing *Arabidopsis* root meristematic cells. Brassinosteroid signaling declines before and during mitosis but recovers in the G1 phase. Single-cell transcriptomic analysis identified brassinosteroid-induced genes that peak in G1, likely driving cell cycle progression. Post-mitotic recovery of brassinosteroid activity is facilitated by non-canonical brassinosteroid signaling activators from the OCTOPUS (OPS) protein family,⁸ which accumulate in a cell cycle-dependent manner and positively regulate cell cycle progression. Due to their polar localization at the apical plasma membrane of the mother cell, brassinosteroid signaling is unevenly triggered in the daughter cells. The upper daughter cells rapidly recover brassinosteroid signaling, while the lower cells express biosynthetic genes, bypassing the negative feedback loop. By integrating genetics with computational modeling, we reveal that these polarity-driven, uneven divisions are essential for optimal root growth.

RESULTS

Brassinosteroid-regulated gene expression fluctuates over the course of the cell cycle in the root apical meristem

While brassinosteroid signaling in the *Arabidopsis* root meristem is linked to cell cycle progression,^{3,5} its dynamics throughout the cell cycle (Figure 1A) remain unexplored. Brassinosteroids regulate thousands of genes via the transcription factors BRASSINAZOLE RESISTANT1 (BZR1) and BR INSENSITIVE EMS SUPPRESSOR1 (BES1), activated upon hormone perception by the BRASSINOSTEROID INSENSITIVE1 (BRI1) receptor.^{9,10} Previous attempts to resolve the role of brassinosteroids in the cell cycle focused on a handful of downstream target genes.^{3,5,11} By contrast, scRNA-seq provides the opportunity to untangle fine-scale changes associated with cell cycle progression across the transcriptome of individual cells.^{12–15} To investigate brassinosteroid activities in proliferating cells, we constructed a cell cycle reference of the *Arabidopsis* root by generating 11 new wild-type scRNA-seq samples. By integrating these with published scRNA-seq samples that were enriched in proliferating cells,^{16,17} we harmonized a cell cycle reference spanning 199,810 cells¹⁸ (Table S1; see STAR Methods). The reference included 52,471 cells in the proliferation domain and proximal

root cap of the meristem, where cell divisions occur frequently. This enabled us to infer a continuous progression of the cell cycle using 245 known cell cycle-associated genes with Tricycle¹⁹ (Figures 1B, 1C, and S1A; Table S1). The resulting scRNA-seq root cell cycle reference captured expression patterns of recently reported markers of G1, S, and G2 to M phases²⁰ (Figures 1D and S1B). We used this reference to define additional markers of each cell cycle phase (Table S1), which were validated by live imaging of transcriptional reporters introduced in the plant cell cycle (PlaCCI)²¹ reporter background (Figures S1C–S1F).

To gain further insight into gene expression patterns across the cell cycle, we focused on atrichoblasts of the epidermis, where brassinosteroid signaling has been linked to meristem activity.⁵ We performed clustering analysis to identify modules of temporally correlated gene expression across the cell cycle (see STAR Methods). We then labeled each module according to the cell cycle phase in which peak expression occurred and examined the overlap with known BES1 and BZR1 targets.^{22–24} We observed an enrichment of BES1 and BZR1 targets that are induced by brassinosteroids in G1-Module 2 (Figures 1E–1G; Table S1). These 294 genes included well-established outputs of brassinosteroid signaling, such as *CSI1*, *CESA6*, and *MYB30*^{25,26} (Figure S2A). The expression of these genes increased early in the cell cycle during the G1 phase but decreased during the G2-to-M transition. By contrast, targets of MYB3R4, a transcription factor known to control G2-to-M gene expression downstream of cytokinins,^{27,28} were enriched in G2-to-M-Module 6 (Figure 1G). These findings suggested that brassinosteroid signaling increases at the onset of the G1 phase but decreases before mitosis.

A key advantage of the cell cycle reference is its ability to project additional datasets and infer each cell's position in the cell cycle. Using this approach, we reanalyzed a published scRNA-seq time series of brassinosteroid response in roots.²⁵ This confirmed that exogenous brassinosteroids promote the expression of the 294 BES1- and BZR1-induced targets from G1-Module 2, extending their expression across the cell cycle (Figures S2B and S2C). We also observed altered expression of brassinosteroid-regulated core cell cycle genes such as *CYCD3;1*²⁹ and *CYCP3;1*,¹¹ which control G1-to-S and G2-to-M transitions, respectively (Figure S2D). Additionally, brassinosteroid treatment upregulated cell cycle regulators such as *CDC48A*³⁰ and *PLT1*³¹ (Figure S2D). However, prolonged brassinosteroid treatment reduced *CDKB1;1* expression, which promotes mitosis by inhibiting endoreduplication,³² and increased *CCS52A1* (Figure S2D), which promotes the transition from mitosis to the endocycle during differentiation.³³

By distinguishing mitotic cells from those undergoing endoreduplication, which is a differentiation-associated process (Figures S2E–S2H), we found that brassinosteroid signaling fluctuates mainly in mitotic cells within the proliferation domain

(G) Enrichment of brassinosteroid (BR)-regulated genes targeted by BES1 and BZR1 that show a peak in brassinosteroid-induced gene expression in G1-Module2 (G1-Mod2), whereas MYB3R4-target genes are enriched in G2/M-Module6 (G2/M-Mod6). Colors represent $-\log_{10} p$ values from the indicated overlaps, calculated from Fisher's exact test by GeneOverlap. The number of genes in each intersection is indicated within each box. WT, wild-type. See also Figures S1 and S2.

(Figure S2I). By contrast, the expression of 294 brassinosteroid-induced BES1 and BZR1 targets remained high during the endocycle and did not decline in G2 (Figure S2I), suggesting that sustained brassinosteroid signaling coincides with cell cycle exit.

These data reveal that brassinosteroid activity fluctuates throughout the cell cycle. Single-cell analysis identifies a set of brassinosteroid-induced genes that peak in early G1 phase and decline as the cell cycle progresses to G2-M. Conversely, cell cycle exit is marked by stable brassinosteroid activity.

Time-lapse imaging reveals nuclear-cytoplasmic shuttling of brassinosteroid signaling regulators during the cell cycle

To determine whether brassinosteroid signaling dynamics explain fluctuations in BES1 and BZR1 target gene expression, we employed live-cell imaging. A vertical microscope setup with automatic root tracking software³⁴ was used to record cell divisions. Nuclear accumulation of BES1 and BZR1⁹ (Figure 2A) served as a readout for brassinosteroid signaling activation.⁴ We observed a decline in BZR1-yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) signal before, during, and immediately after mitosis (Figures 2B, 2C, and S3A), followed by a gradual increase starting approximately 30 min post-mitosis, peaking at 120 min in root epidermal cells (Figures 2C and S3A; Video S1). A similar pattern was detected in root cortical and phloem cells (Figures S3B and S3C). To further analyze BZR1 dynamics, we used a reporter line co-expressing BZR1-mCherry and the G1-phase marker CDT1a-GFP.³⁵ Long-term imaging showed that BZR1-mCherry nuclear accumulation peaked in the G1 phase (Figure 2D). Similarly, BES1, in a line co-expressing BES1-Ypet, H2B-mCherry (nuclear marker), and CDT1a-CFP, peaked at around 120 min post-mitosis, preceding CDT1a-CFP accumulation (Figures S3D and S3E). These findings indicate that brassinosteroid signaling fluctuates throughout the cell cycle, decreasing during mitosis and increasing in G1.

We hypothesized that the reduction in nuclear BZR1 and BES1 localization and the corresponding signaling decrease during mitosis result from the activity of negative regulators of brassinosteroid signaling from the *Arabidopsis thaliana* SHAGGY-related protein kinases (ATSKs) family. ATSK21/BRASSINOSTEROID-INSENSITIVE2 (BIN2), ATSK11, and ATSK32 phosphorylate BZR1 and BES1 in the nucleus, leading to their inactivation and cytoplasmic displacement^{36,37} (Figure 2A). However, how this regulation occurs throughout the cell cycle remains unclear. To investigate the role of ATSK in controlling BZR1 levels during mitotic divisions, we conducted high-temporal-resolution imaging, focusing on pre-mitotic and mitotic stages. In a transgenic line co-expressing both proteins, BZR1-mCherry exclusion from the nucleus signal in prophase coincided with ATSK32-GFP nuclear entry. During telophase, BZR1-mCherry re-entered newly formed nuclei only after ATSK32-GFP disappeared (Figure 2E). Similar localization patterns were observed for other ATSK family members during mitosis (Figure S3F).

In summary, live-cell imaging revealed dynamic BZR1 and BES1 nuclear accumulation across the cell cycle. Their nuclear levels decline before, during, and immediately after mitosis, coinciding with ATSK nuclear entry. After cytokinesis, BZR1 and BES1 rapidly reaccumulated in daughter cell nuclei during

G1, driving the transcriptional regulation of their target genes in this cell cycle phase (Figure 1G).

Brassinosteroid biosynthetic enzymes accumulate in the lower daughter cell following anticlinal symmetric cell division

Brassinosteroid signaling activation inhibits brassinosteroid biosynthesis^{23,38} (Figure 2A). To investigate how this feedback loop operates during and after cell division, we analyzed the expression dynamics of *DWARF4* (*DWF4*), a BES1- and BZR1-regulated brassinosteroid biosynthetic gene.³⁸ Our cell cycle analysis revealed that *DWF4*, despite being repressed by brassinosteroid signaling, fluctuates and increases in G1 following cell division (Figure 3A). This raises the question of how both brassinosteroid biosynthesis and signaling can increase simultaneously, given that signaling should inhibit biosynthesis through a feedback loop.

Live-cell imaging of *DWF4*-GFP expressed under its native promoter showed a patchy GFP pattern in proliferating root epidermal cells (Figure 3B). Surprisingly, the *DWF4*-GFP signal was most prominent in the lower daughter cell around 180 min post-mitosis (Figures 3C and S4A; Video S2). This peak in *DWF4*-GFP accumulation was transient. In subsequent divisions, *DWF4*-GFP again increased in the lower daughter cells (Figure S4B). The differential *DWF4*-GFP accumulation was transcriptionally regulated, as no patchy expression was observed when the fusion protein was ectopically expressed under the *WEREWOLF* (*WER*) epidermis-specific promoter (Figures S4C and S4F). To determine if this pattern was specific to *DWF4*, we examined the expression of other brassinosteroid biosynthetic enzymes. Both CONSTITUTIVE PHOTOMORPHOGENIC DWARF (*CPD*)³⁹ and BRASSINOSTEROID-6-OXIDASE2 (*BR6OX2*)⁴⁰ showed a similar uneven pattern in daughter cells (Figures S4D, S4E, S4G, and S4H) in the stele and endodermis, respectively. A similar pattern was also observed in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) roots expressing *SlCPD*-GFP under its native promoter (Figures S4I and S4J). These findings highlight dynamic spatiotemporal transcriptional control of brassinosteroid biosynthetic enzymes in the root meristem.

Uneven brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis in daughter cells after cell division are linked to the unequal distribution of brassinosteroid signaling components

We next hypothesized that the differential expression of brassinosteroid biosynthetic enzymes in the newly formed daughter cells is a result of the uneven distribution of brassinosteroid signaling components. In agreement, re-examination of the BZR1-YFP line (Figure 2B) and separate quantification of fluorescence signal in upper and lower daughter cells after cell division revealed a higher accumulation of the fluorescence signal in the nuclei of the upper daughter cells (Figures S4K–S4M). The contrasting BZR1 nuclear localization between the upper and lower daughter cells preceded the differential accumulation of *DWF4* enzyme, as seen in the dual-color *DWF4*-GFP/BZR1-mCherry marker line (Figures 3D and 3E). We confirmed differences between the upper and lower daughter cells by examining the nuclear signal ratio between BZR1-YFP and a nuclear marker

Figure 2. Localization of brassinosteroid signaling components dynamically changes during the cell cycle

(A) A simplified illustration of the brassinosteroid signaling pathway and the negative feedback loop repressing brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes. (B) Co-expression of BZR1-YFP under its native promoter with the plasma membrane marker *pUBQ10:RCI2A::tdTomato*. (C) Quantification of the nuclear BZR1-YFP signal in daughter cells following cell division in *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP/pUBQ10:RCI2A::tdTomato* transgenic line shown in (B), $n = 48$, n , number of cell division events analyzed. The shades around the line represent 95% confidence interval. a.u., arbitrary unit. (D) Long-term confocal imaging of roots co-expressing *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and the G1 phase marker *pCDT1a:CDT1a-GFP*. BZR1-YFP nuclear accumulation increases after cell division, during the G1 phase. Two cell division events are shown. Lines indicate G1 phase in each daughter cell. (E) High-temporal-resolution analysis of BZR1-mCherry and ATSK32-GFP dynamics during mitosis in root epidermal cells shows that BZR1-mCherry exits the nucleus in prophase, preceded by the ATSK32-GFP nuclear entry. In telophase, the BZR1-mCherry enters the newly formed nuclei only after the ATSK32-GFP exit. Time point 0 indicates start of mitosis. Single z sections of the root epidermal cells are shown (B, D, and E). Scale bars, 10 μm in (B) and 5 μm in (D) and (E).

See also [Figure S3](#).

nuclear localization signal (NLS)-tdTomato (Figures 3F and 3G). In addition, inducible expression of the dominant version of the BES1 transcription factor, BES1-D-mCherry, completely suppressed DWF4-GFP accumulation (Figure S4N). BES1-GFP reporter lines exhibited a similar localization pattern to BZR1 (Figure S5A).

To further investigate the mechanism underlying the differential accumulation of BZR1 and BES1 in daughter cells, we examined the behavior of these transcription factors when expressed under the control of a constitutive 35S promoter. Both BZR1-YFP and BES1-GFP were unevenly distributed between the daughter cell nuclei following cell division. This finding suggests that transcriptional regulation is not the primary factor responsible for the differential protein accumulation (Figures S5B, S5C, S5E, and S5F), although we cannot rule out its contribution, as BZR1 and BES1 are known to induce their own transcription

through a self-amplification mechanism.²³ Additionally, treatment with the proteasome inhibitor MG132, which stabilizes BZR1,⁴¹ did not prevent differential protein accumulation after cell divisions in the *p35S:BZR1-YFP* line (Figures S5D and S5G). Thus, it is plausible that the phosphorylation status of BZR1 and BES1, which determines their nuclear shuttling, rather than their transcriptional regulation or protein degradation, serves as the primary mechanism driving their unequal accumulation in the daughter cell nuclei, a feature not observed for unrelated transcription factors (Figures S5H and S5I).

Subsequently, we sought to determine which brassinosteroid signaling components upstream of BZR1 and BES1 are responsible for this pattern. We examined the accumulation of the plasma membrane-localized BRI1 receptor in the daughter cell pairs. BRI1-mCitrine accumulation did not show an apparent

Figure 3. Upper and lower daughter cells exhibit different accumulation of brassinosteroid biosynthetic and signaling components

(A) Expression pattern of brassinosteroid biosynthetic gene *DWF4* in proliferation domain atrichoblasts of the wild-type cell cycle reference.
 (B) A patchy accumulation pattern of *DWF4*-GFP enzyme expressed under the control of its native promoter. Cell walls were stained with propidium iodide (PI).
 (C) Quantification of *DWF4*-GFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells after cell division in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/pUBQ10:RC12A:tdTomato* marker line, $n = 20$.
 (D) Long-term confocal imaging of *DWF4*-GFP and *BZR1*-mCherry dual marker expressing fluorescent proteins under the control of their native promoters.
 (E) Quantification of *DWF4*-GFP and *BZR1*-mCherry signal in upper and lower daughter cells after cell division in dual marker line shown in (D), $n = 18$.
 (F) Long-term confocal imaging of roots co-expressing *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and the nuclear marker *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato*.
 (G) Quantification of *BZR1*-YFP and *NLS*-tdTomato signal ratios in the nuclei of the upper and lower daughter cells, before and after cell division shown in (F), $n = 28$.
 (H) Long-term confocal imaging of roots co-expressing *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* and the nuclear marker *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato*.
 (I) Quantification of *ATSK32*-GFP and *NLS*-tdTomato signal ratios in the nuclei of upper and lower daughter cells, before and after cell divisions shown in (H), $n = 37$.
 (J) Quantification of *ATSK32*-GFP cytoplasmic signal in upper and lower daughter cells, before and after cell divisions shown in (H), $n = 37$.
 Single z sections of the root epidermal cells are shown (B, D, F, and H). Scale bars, 20 μ m in (B) and 5 μ m in (D), (F), and (H). n , number of cell division events analyzed (C, E, G, I, and J). The shades around lines represent 95% confidence interval (see STAR Methods), a.u., arbitrary unit (C, E, G, I, and J).
 See also Figures S4 and S5.

Figure 4. An intrinsic cell polarity orchestrates the differential accumulation of DWF4 and BZR1 in the daughter cells following cell division
(A) A hypothetical scenario explaining differential levels of brassinosteroid (BR) signaling in the upper and lower daughter cells after cell division.
(B) Ectopically expressed mCherry-BASL preferentially localizes to the basal plasma membrane (PM) of the lower daughter cell following division, where DWF4-GFP also accumulates.
(C) Long-term confocal imaging of DWF4-GFP expressed under its native promoter in *dGR* background following 10 μ M dexamethasone (DEX) induction. Two simultaneous cell divisions are shown, one anticlinal and one radial.

(legend continued on next page)

difference between daughter cells following cell division (Figure S5J). This implies that the differential distribution of the receptor is unlikely to be the cause of unequal expression of biosynthetic enzymes in the daughter cells. Given their roles as negative regulators of BES1 and BZR1,³⁶ we reasoned that the unequal ATSK(s) distribution in the newly formed daughter cells might drive the differential nuclear accumulation of these transcription factors. BZR1 phosphorylation by ATSK21/BIN2 takes place in the nucleus,⁴² where all examined ATSKs are localized transiently during mitosis (Figures 2E and S3F). However, in order to regulate brassinosteroid signaling after mitosis, these kinases would also need to be localized in the nucleus in interphase cells. Therefore, we observed the subcellular localization of nine of the ten ATSKs during interphase in root meristematic cells (Figure S5K). Of those tested, ATSK32-GFP had the most prominent nuclear localization in the interphase nuclei of the root meristem (Figure S5L), although we cannot exclude the nuclear presence of other ATSKs at lower levels. ATSK32-GFP protein localized to the nucleus when brassinosteroid signaling levels were low (Figure S5M), and long-term imaging revealed that both nuclear and cytoplasmic accumulation was more prominent in the lower daughter cell following cell division (Figures 3H–3J; Video S3).

To investigate whether the uneven accumulation of ATSK32 contributes to differential brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis in daughter cells following cell division, we generated a double *atsk31/atsk32* CRISPR mutant in the *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* background. We did not observe noticeable root growth phenotypes (Figures S5N–S5P), likely due to the redundant function with other ATSKs. Therefore, we employed the ATSK inhibitor—bikinin,⁴³ which does not target ATSK31 and ATSK32,⁴⁴ to probe the functions of other ATSKs. *atsk31/atsk32* showed a higher sensitivity to bikinin in suppression of root growth, DWF4-GFP accumulation, and meristem morphology, with phenotypes resembling those of roots with elevated brassinosteroid signaling⁶ (Figures S5N–S5S). These results indicate that ATSK32, and likely other ATSKs, are responsible for the uneven distribution of BZR1 and BES1, ultimately leading to preferential expression of brassinosteroid biosynthetic enzymes in the lower daughter cell after cell division.

Intrinsic cell polarity is a key determinant of the differential brassinosteroid signaling after division

Differential gene expression in daughter cells can lead to asymmetric divisions that give rise to distinct tissue and cell types.⁴⁵ In

Arabidopsis roots, anticlinal cell divisions are symmetric, producing cells of the same fate. Nevertheless, the unequal accumulation of brassinosteroid signaling components and biosynthetic enzymes indicates that these divisions generate physiologically distinct cells. One explanation for this phenomenon could be that the daughter cells inherit an unequal amount of certain molecular components due to the intrinsic apical-basal polarity of the mother cell (Figure 4A). To examine the probable intrinsic polarity of the amplifying cells, we analyzed the localization of the stomata lineage-specific protein BREAKING OF ASYMMETRY IN THE STOMATAL LINEAGE (BASL), which can reveal polarized regions in various plant cell types.⁴⁶ When expressed ectopically in the root meristem, mCherry-BASL accumulated almost exclusively in the lower cell of the daughter cell pair together with DWF4-GFP, exposing intrinsic cell polarity (Figure 4B). Next, we examined the DWF4-GFP accumulation following radial cell division of root epidermal cells. To this end, we crossed *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* with the *dGR* line, where TARGET OF MONOPTEROS5 (TMO5) and LONESOME HIGHWAY (LHW) pair of transcription factors can be expressed in an inducible manner, sufficient to generate periclinal and radial cell divisions in *Arabidopsis* root meristem.⁴⁷ After radial cell divisions, no differential DWF4-GFP accumulation was observed (Figures 4C and 4D), suggesting that an apical-basal intrinsic cell polarity regulates contrasting brassinosteroid hormone activity in daughter cells. Based on these observations, we predicted that polarly localized proteins control brassinosteroid signaling during and immediately after mitosis.

OPS protein family members positively regulate brassinosteroid signaling after cell division

OPS-LIKE (OPL) family members are membrane-associated, apically localized proteins that positively regulate brassinosteroid signaling.^{48,49} OPS and OPL proteins are predominantly expressed in the *Arabidopsis* root apical meristem⁵⁰ (Figure 4E), making them prime candidates for regulating brassinosteroid signaling in proliferating cells.

We employed long-term live-cell imaging to monitor the localization and dynamics of OPL2-GFP expressed under the control of its native promoter in root epidermal cells. In agreement with scRNA-seq analysis where *OPL2* expression showed cell-cycle dependence (Figure 4F), the OPL2-GFP signal started to appear in the mother cell before and during cytokinesis and reached an accumulation peak in daughter cells immediately after cell division (Figures 4G and 4H; Video S4). In addition to the polar

(D) Quantification of DWF4-GFP signal in the daughter cells from radial divisions and upper and lower daughter cells from anticlinal divisions shown in (C). Signal intensity was measured 180 min after cell divisions. a.u., arbitrary unit.

(E) Expression of OPL2-GFP in root meristem under the control of its native promoter. Root was stained with propidium iodide.

(F) Expression pattern of *OPL2* in atrichoblast cells in proliferation domain of the WT cell cycle reference.

(G) Long-term confocal imaging of plants co-expressing OPL2-GFP and BZR1-mCherry under their native promoters.

(H) High-temporal-resolution analysis of OPL2-GFP dynamics during cytokinesis with the cell plate labeled with FM4-64 dye. OPL2-GFP localizes to the apical PM domain of the mother cell before and during cytokinesis, then moves to the cell plate and later to the nascent cell wall between two daughter cells.

(I) OPL2-GFP cytoplasmic accumulation is more pronounced in the upper daughter cells after anticlinal cell divisions.

(J) Quantification of OPL2-GFP signal in the upper and lower daughter cells after the anticlinal divisions as shown in (I). Signal intensity was measured 100 min after cell divisions. a.u., arbitrary unit. A two-tailed paired t test analysis was used to determine statistical significance in (D) and (J). All individual data points are plotted. *n*, number of cell divisions analyzed. n.s., not significant.

Single z sections of the root epidermal cells are shown (B, C, and G–I). Scale bars, 10 μ m in (B), 5 μ m in (C), (G), and (H), and 20 μ m in (E).

See also Figure S6.

Figure 5. OPS and OPL2 interact with ATSKs to regulate their localization and abundance

(A) Constitutive OPL2-mCherry overexpression reduces ATSK32-GFP nuclear localization and induces its polarized plasma membrane (PM) localization. (B) Long-term confocal imaging of roots overexpressing OPL2-mCherry in *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* background (bottom) shows co-localization of both proteins at the cell plate and at the apical PM during cell divisions. While ATSK32-GFP exhibits nuclear localization when expressed alone (top). (C) Inducible overexpression of *pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-mCherry* in the *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* background decreases ATSK32-GFP protein levels as detected in (D). (D) ATSK32-GFP protein accumulation was detected by immunoblotting with anti-GFP (α -GFP) antibody. Tubulin was detected with anti-tubulin (α -tubulin) antibody and was used as a reference. OPS-mCherry protein was detected with anti-mRFP (α -mRFP) antibody. Relative ATSK32-GFP protein levels from four replicates were analyzed with symbols denoting individual samples and bars indicating SD. Significant differences were determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's multiple comparison tests.

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localization at the apical plasma membrane, OPL2-GFP also accumulated in the cytoplasm of the upper daughter cell after cell divisions (Figures 4I and 4J). This could be due to the relocalization of the protein from the cell plate⁵⁰ to the apical polar domain of the upper daughter cell (Figure 4H). The increased OPL2-GFP accumulation preceded BZR1-mCherry nuclear accumulation (Figure 4G; Video S4), suggesting that OPL2, and likely its homologs, are associated with the unequal brassinosteroid signaling in the two daughter cells after cell division.

OPS was shown to activate brassinosteroid signaling through direct interaction and sequestration of ATSK21/BIN2 to the plasma membrane, allowing the nuclear accumulation of BES1 and BZR1.⁴⁹ Thus, we next examined the effects of gain-of-function *OPS* and *OPL2* on brassinosteroid activity in daughter cells following cell division. On one hand, constitutive overexpression of OPL2-mCherry led to a sharp decrease in DWF4-GFP signal (Figure S6A), indicating high brassinosteroid signaling levels that override the differences between newly formed cells. On the other hand, altered brassinosteroid signaling did not significantly affect OPS and OPL2 protein levels (Figures S6B and S6C). Increased brassinosteroid signaling levels upon OPL2 overexpression are likely a consequence of a reduced nuclear pool of ATSK32, caused by the relocalization of the kinase to the plasma membrane in both daughter cells (Figures 5A and 5B), through a direct interaction with OPS and OPL2 (Figures 5C, 5E, and 5F). We also observed an overall reduction of ATSK32-GFP protein levels when either OPS or OPL2 were overexpressed (Figures 5A–5D), which presents an additional mechanism of ATSK(s) regulation by these scaffolds. Moreover, imaging of a double marker line expressing ATSK32-GFP and OPL2-mCherry under their native promoters revealed contrasting protein accumulation patterns in the newly formed daughter cells (Figure 5G). To exclude the possibility of transcriptional regulation of ATSK32 levels in daughter cells, we expressed ATSK32-mCherry under a cytokinesis-specific *KNOLLE* (*KN*) promoter.⁵¹ Again, we observed higher ATSK32 protein accumulation in the lower daughter cell, indicating that ATSK32 protein levels are regulated post-transcriptionally following cell division (Figure 5H).

These data collectively demonstrate that OPL protein accumulation increases in the upper daughter cells after cell division. There, OPL proteins interact with and negatively regulate ATSK activity through nuclear exclusion and degradation, leading to increased brassinosteroid signaling.

The OPL-brassinosteroid signaling module accelerates cell division in the protophloem

Similarly to epidermal cells, OPS-GFP and OPL2-GFP accumulated to a greater extent in the upper daughter cells within proto-

phloem proliferation domain (Figures S6D and S6E), referred to as the amplification zone.⁵² Because the differential BZR1 nuclear accumulation between upper and lower daughter cells was particularly pronounced in protophloem (Figure S3C), where OPS and OPL2 play an important developmental role, we focused on this tissue with the goal of identifying the transcriptional signatures of upper and lower daughter cells. We first determined whether the molecular signature of increased brassinosteroid activity could be detected in phloem by reanalyzing scRNA-seq data derived from a phloem pole atlas.⁵³ Using the cell cycle reference, we annotated the progression of 3,645 meristematic phloem cells from this dataset (Figure S6F). Through clustering analysis, we identified a group of genes expressed in G1 with enriched BES1 and BZR1 target expression, including 419 brassinosteroid-induced genes (Figures S6G–S6I; Table S1). This confirms that the cell cycle-related fluctuations in brassinosteroid-regulated gene expression can also be detected in phloem cells. We hypothesized that the brassinosteroid-induced versus brassinosteroid biosynthesis genes are expressed in the upper versus lower cells, respectively. Thus, we analyzed the top 10% of cells in G1 with each of these signatures as potential upper versus lower cells. Contrasting the expression patterns of these groups of cells allowed us to identify enriched genes and associated biological processes (Table S1). Consistent with high brassinosteroid signaling levels, putative upper cells are enriched for the Gene Ontology (GO) term “Cell wall organization or biogenesis” (Figure S6J) and have increased expression of *CESA6* and *CS11* (Figure S6K). On the other hand, the expression of brassinosteroid-repressed genes *CPD* and *DWF4* was higher in the putative lower cells, which were associated with translation and biosynthetic processes (Figure S6K). In combination with our live imaging, these data support the occurrence of distinct cellular states in the phloem in terms of brassinosteroid signaling versus biosynthesis following cell division.

Next, we examined the effects of loss-of-function *OPS* and *OPL2* on brassinosteroid activity in daughter cells after cell divisions in phloem. To overcome the possible pleiotropic meristem defects in *ops/opl2* mutant caused by dysfunctional phloem transport,⁸ we generated an estradiol-inducible CRISPR-Cas9 system to simultaneously knock out *OPS* and *OPL2* (*XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR*) in a rapid, inducible fashion (Figures S7A and S7B; see STAR Methods). We then monitored the BZR1-YFP localization during cell division in the inducible double CRISPR knockout *OPS* and *OPL2* mutant (Figure S7C). BZR1-YFP in the protophloem amplification zone was mostly cytoplasmic and remained excluded from the nucleus in both upper and lower daughter cells of the inducible *OPS* and *OPL2* CRISPR mutant (Figures 6A and 6B). This indicates that OPS and OPL2 mediate the unequal brassinosteroid signaling following cell division in

(E) Förster resonance energy transfer by fluorescence lifetime imaging (FRET-FLIM) analysis reveals direct interaction between ATSK32-GFP and OPS-mCherry in the cytoplasm and at the PM. All individual data points are plotted. Horizontal bars represent the means, and error bars represent SD. *n*, number of root epidermal cells analyzed. A two-tailed Student's unpaired t test analysis was used to determine the significant differences.

(F) ATSK32 and BIN2 co-immunoprecipitated with OPL2 when transiently co-expressed in tobacco leaves. IP, immunoprecipitation; IB, immunoblot.

(G) Long-term confocal imaging of dual lines expressing ATSK32-GFP and OPL2-mCherry under the control of their native promoters.

(H) Long-term confocal imaging of a line expressing ATSK32-mCherry under the control of *KN* promoter.

Single z sections of the root epidermal cells are shown (A–C, G, and H). Scale bars, 20 μ m in (A), 5 μ m in (B), (G), and (H), and 10 μ m (C).

See also Figure S6.

Figure 6. OPS- and OPL2-dependent brassinosteroid signaling activation positively regulates cell cycle progression

(A) Protophloem developmental zones in the *Arabidopsis* root meristem.

(B) BZR1-YFP localization dynamics in dividing protophloem cells of inducible CRISPR-mediated OPS and OPL2 knockout mutants. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to fresh medium with 10 μ M estradiol for 24 h before overnight imaging.

(C) Protophloem cells of *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and *XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR/pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* lines, after 40 h induction with 10 μ M estradiol. Arrowheads indicate anticlinal cell walls. Cell walls were stained with PI.

(D) Quantification of the cortical cell length shown in (C).

(E) Quantification of the cell cycle duration of cortical cells in control *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* and *XVE:OPS-mCherry/pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* lines. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to a fresh medium containing 10 μ M estradiol and imaged immediately using a vertical microscope setup. Individual cells were tracked from division to division, and cell cycle time was recorded.

(F) A newly formed cortical cell pair, immediately after cell division.

(G) Quantification of the cortical cell length at the time of cell division. Comparison between *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* and *XVE:OPS-mCherry/pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* lines is shown.

(H) Quantification of the cell cycle duration. Comparison of cortical and protophloem cells.

A two-tailed Student's unpaired t test analysis was used to determine the significant difference (D, E, G, and H). *n*, number of cells analyzed. Individual data points are plotted, horizontal bars represent the means, and error bars indicate SD.

Single z sections are shown (B and C). Scale bars, 5 μ m in (B) and (F) and 10 μ m in (C).

See also [Figure S7](#).

the protophloem. We detected longer protophloem cells upon CRISPR knockout of *OPS* and *OPL2* (Figures 6C and 6D) and repeatedly observed cells in the protophloem amplification zone that no longer divided after CRISPR induction (Figure S7D), which is an indication that *OPS* and *OPL2* are required for the transit-amplifying cell divisions. Based on these phenotypes and the previously reported role of *OPL2* in promoting cell divisions in stomatal lineage,⁵⁰ we postulated that the *OPS*- and *OPL2*-dependent brassinosteroid signaling module promotes cell cycle progression in the root. To test this hypothesis, we overexpressed *OPS-mCherry* in an inducible manner and measured the duration of the cell cycle of root cortical cells. Indeed, overexpression of *OPS* reduced the time between two successive cell divisions (Figure 6E), and cells divided at a signif-

icantly smaller size compared with the mock control (Figures 6F and 6G).

The observed phloem phenotype in the inducible CRISPR mutant can be correlated with the strong *OPS* expression in the protophloem, where its domain overlaps with *OPL2* expression and where the highest nuclear intensity of *BZR1* was observed (Figure S7E). We hypothesized that protophloem cells might have a shorter cell cycle that is driven by *OPS* and *OPL2*-induced brassinosteroid signaling. Long-term confocal imaging confirmed this hypothesis and revealed that the cell cycle of the cells in the protophloem amplification zone is around two times shorter than that of the cortical cells (Figure 6H).

These findings demonstrate that *OPS* and *OPL2*-mediated brassinosteroid signaling activation promotes cell cycle

Figure 7. Computational modeling simulations of the growth of the *Arabidopsis* root meristem reveal importance of brassinosteroid signaling fluctuations

(A) Three scenarios for the computational model of *Arabidopsis* root simulations. Scenario 1: no drop in brassinosteroid (BR) signaling after cell division; brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes are not expressed due to feedback inhibition. Scenario 2: a drop in brassinosteroid signaling in both daughter cells post-division allows equal expression of brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes with signaling recovering equally in the two daughter cells after a delay. Scenario 3: brassinosteroid signaling decreases in both daughter cells post-division but recovers immediately in one, allowing the other cell to express brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes after a delayed recovery.

(B) Root cell divisions for different scenarios and time delays: scenario 1 shows the fewest cell divisions. In scenario 2, longer time delays reduce cell division counts. Scenario 3 exhibits more cell divisions in the meristems, which remain stable despite changes in signaling delay intervals. No differences occur when switching signaling and biosynthesis between upper and lower daughter cells.

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progression in the *Arabidopsis* root apical meristem. The role of OPS and OPL2 is particularly prominent in the protophloem, a root tissue with rapid cell divisions, high brassinosteroid signaling, and a pronounced difference in brassinosteroid signaling levels between upper and lower daughter cells following cell divisions.

Division of brassinosteroid biosynthesis and signaling labor in daughter cells ensures optimal root growth

How does unequal brassinosteroid signaling between upper and lower daughter cells after mitosis contribute to optimal organ growth? One explanation is that it balances the reestablishment of signaling and hormone biosynthesis. In one daughter cell, brassinosteroid signaling is rapidly restored, while the other maintains low signaling, allowing brassinosteroid biosynthetic gene expression and hormone production needed for meristem activity. To test this hypothesis, we used spatiotemporal computational modeling to simulate *Arabidopsis* root meristem growth based on a recent mechano-biochemical model.⁵⁴ Our model integrates brassinosteroid signaling-dependent cell growth, hormone diffusion, cell division-boosted hormone production, and post-division signaling recovery (see STAR Methods). We examined three scenarios of brassinosteroid signaling post-division (Figure 7A). Scenario 1 assumes no changes in brassinosteroid signaling, and brassinosteroid biosynthetic gene expression remains repressed. Scenario 2 considers a symmetric recovery, where both daughter cells maintain low signaling post-division and recover simultaneously after a set delay leading to hormone precursor diffusion. Finally, scenario 3 tests asymmetric recovery, where signaling rapidly restores in one daughter cell, while the other cell produces brassinosteroid precursors and recovers signaling more slowly. Simulations showed significantly reduced division and root growth rates for scenario 1. In scenario 2, root growth was sensitive to recovery delays, with longer delays reducing overall root growth. Notably, scenario 3 predicted robust root growth even with extended delays (Figures 7B and 7C; Video S5). Switching rapid signaling reestablishment from upper to lower daughter cell yielded similar results, suggesting differential brassinosteroid biosynthesis and signaling in daughter cells after cell division optimizes root growth.

To test our model predictions, we examined the impact of equal brassinosteroid signaling or biosynthesis recovery in daughter cells on root growth. We expressed the dominant BES1-D-mCherry under the cytokinesis-specific *KN* promoter

in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* background, enabling protein accumulation during and immediately after mitosis.⁵¹ BES1-D-mCherry localized equally in nuclei of both daughter cells, while the DWF4-GFP expression in the meristem was almost completely suppressed (Figure 7D; Video S5), leading to reduced root growth and meristem cell production compared with the control (Figures 7E and 7F). This highlights the importance of unequal brassinosteroid signaling recovery in daughter cells for coordinated signaling and biosynthesis, ensuring optimal root growth. Next, we analyzed a transgenic line where brassinosteroid biosynthesis was uncoupled from signaling by expression of *pWER:DWF4-GFP* in the meristematic epidermis of the *dwf4* mutant.⁶ Instead of one cell exhibiting high signaling while the other engages in biosynthesis, both cells expressed DWF4-GFP evenly (Figure 7G). Previously, we showed that these lines exhibit traits of increased brassinosteroid signaling, such as elongated cortical cells and reduced meristem width.⁶ Here, we demonstrate that elevated brassinosteroid levels negatively affect meristem activity, as indicated by reduced cell production rates (Figure 7H).

DISCUSSION

Recent studies on brassinosteroid hormones highlight their potential to boost crop yields,^{55–58} yet the dynamics and spatiotemporal control of brassinosteroid activity in proliferating cells remain elusive, even in model plants. Here, we show that brassinosteroid activity, essential for both cell expansion and proliferation during plant growth,¹⁰ fluctuates throughout the cell cycle in the *Arabidopsis* root meristem. Brassinosteroid signaling declines prior to and during mitosis, then increases early in the G1 phase. scRNA-seq analysis of the cell cycle revealed transcriptional effects of fluctuating brassinosteroid signaling, identifying core cell cycle components that may act as effectors to ensure progression and rhythmic expression of mitotic genes. Increased brassinosteroid signaling during the G1 phase may be crucial for cell expansion to an optimal size for mitosis, in addition to influencing cell cycle-related gene expression. A size-controlled mechanism involving the cell cycle inhibitor KIP-RELATED PROTEIN4 adjusts the growth period before DNA synthesis to buffer cell size variability in the shoot apical meristem.⁵⁹ It remains unclear if a similar process operates in roots and how brassinosteroids might affect it. Given that brassinosteroids regulate root meristem cell anisotropy rather than

(C) Predicted root growth rates from computational models for different scenarios and time delays for brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis levels in newly divided root meristem cells. Each panel represents the set time delay for brassinosteroid signaling recovery after cell division.

(D) Long-term confocal imaging of root epidermal cells expressing *pKNOLLE (KN):BES1-D-mCherry* in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* background reveals the absence of DWF4-GFP signal, unlike the accumulation observed in the lower daughter cell of the control line.

(E) Comparison of root growth rates of *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* and *pKN:BES1-D-mCherry/pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* plants shown in (D). Values represent means \pm SD of root growth rates.

(F) Quantification of the root meristem cortical cell production rates for *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* and *pKN:BES1-D-mCherry/pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* lines shown in (D). A two-tailed Student's unpaired t test analysis was used to determine the significant difference.

(G) Accumulation pattern of DWF4-GFP expressed under its native and *WEREWOLF (WER)* promoters in the *dwf4* mutant background.

(H) Quantification of the root meristem cortical cell production rates for roots shown in (G). Significant differences between Col-0 and the transgenic lines were determined by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison tests. For (F) and (H), all individual data points are plotted. Horizontal bars represent the means, and error bars represent SD. *n*, number of roots analyzed (E, F, and H).

Single z sections are shown (D). Scale bars, 5 μ m in (D) and 20 μ m in (F).

See also Figure S7.

cell volume,⁶⁰ it is possible that cell shape also influences the timing of cell divisions.

scRNA-seq analysis revealed that rhythmic expression of brassinosteroid target genes ceases when cells transition from the mitotic cycle to the endocycle as they move from the meristem to the elongation zone. This explains why both hormone deficiency and hyperactive signaling reduce mitotic activity in the root meristem due to varying brassinosteroid requirements at different cell cycle stages. High brassinosteroid biosynthesis and signaling are linked to cell cycle exit and subsequent cell expansion,⁶ but it remains unclear how they coexist in the root elongation zone, despite the strong negative feedback loop.

In dividing cells of the root apical meristem, the brassinosteroid negative feedback loop maintains low but sufficient brassinosteroid activity. The decrease in signaling during mitosis is reflected by upregulated biosynthetic enzymes in newly formed cells, mainly in the lower daughter cell. This upregulation results from the polar localization of OPS and OPL2 proteins to the apical cell membrane, which facilitates nuclear exclusion and reduces the abundance of certain ATSKs, activating brassinosteroid signaling in the upper daughter cell. Signaling is recovered in the G1, allowing biosynthetic gene expression to proceed despite the negative feedback (Figure S7F). This mechanism, observed in protophloem cells, ensures rapid cell cycle progression and early differentiation, enabling nutrient delivery to the apical meristem.

In developmental biology, asymmetric divisions result in daughter cells with different fates, while symmetric divisions produce daughter cells with the same fate.⁶¹ Differential brassinosteroid signaling is involved in cell fate decisions during asymmetric divisions in the stomatal lineage.^{62,63} Here, we show that in the root, differential brassinosteroid signaling driven by the mother cell's intrinsic polarity defines distinct cellular states after symmetric cell divisions. Computational simulations demonstrate that this mode of division promotes the simultaneous increase in brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis, essential for optimal root meristem activity. It remains to be seen if a similar mechanism operates in other organ meristems.

In summary, our study highlights the role of cell cycle-dependent fluctuations in brassinosteroid activity and reveals that transit-amplifying cells in the root meristem undergo uneven mitotic divisions to balance brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis for optimal root growth. We uncover the complexity of brassinosteroid-regulated development, offering insights for precise engineering of root form and function. The single-cell root cell cycle reference serves as a valuable resource for studying cell-cycle-dependent gene expression and advancing research on other major hormone groups.

Limitations of the study

Although our results show that the single-cell reference of the cell cycle captures G1, S, and G2/M progressions, we did not observe a cyclic, continuous progression from S to G2/M, suggesting an abrupt shift in gene expression or technical factors such as insufficient cells at this transition or protoplast isolation effects. Future efforts could integrate live imaging and spatial transcriptomics to link cell states with broader gene expression in a tissue context. We identified polarity-driven uneven post-di-

vision brassinosteroid signaling in daughter cells and, through computational modeling and *in planta* experiments, demonstrated how this mechanism optimizes organ growth. However, phenotypic defects in inducible *ops/opl2* CRISPR mutants were confined to the phloem. Other polar brassinosteroid regulators may drive post-division signaling recovery in other root tissues, which will be a focus of future research. Additionally, uneven brassinosteroid signaling may lead to subtle differences in daughter cell expansion and division rates. Advancements in root imaging, large-scale image analysis, and modeling will be critical in determining whether these subtle differences exist and how they impact overall organ growth.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Requests for further information and resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Eugenia Russinova (eugenia.russinova@psb.vib-ugent.be).

Materials availability

Plasmids and transgenic-line seed materials will be available from the [lead contact](#) upon request.

Data and code availability

- The 10× Genomics scRNA-seq data described in this study are available in NCBI GEO under accession GEO: GSE262840. These data are available in an interactive browser: <https://nolanlab.shinyapps.io/arvex>.
- The code used to analyze scRNA-seq data is available at https://github.com/tmnolan/Brassinosteroid_cell_cycle.
- Long-term confocal microscopy videos are available at this Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748704>.
- Unprocessed blots are available at this Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/14748834>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, N.V., C.-W.H., T.M.N., and E.R.; methodology, N.V., C.-W.H., T.M.N., M.M., C.Z., Z.A., I.V., Q.M., J.C., L.P., P.K., N.G., J.Z., C.S.-V., J.P.-S., P.C.Q., Q.Z., L.R.L., J.C., and E.T.; investigation, N.V., T.M.N., Z.A., Q.M., J.C., L.P., P.K., M.M., and E.T.; data analysis, N.V., C.-W.H., T.M.N., M.M., S.L., R.S., P.S., L.R.L., Z.A., P.K., M.F., and K.W.; supervision, N.V., E.M.B., M.F., Y.Z., S.S.-G., K.W., T.M.N., and E.R.; writing – original draft, N.V., C.-W.H., K.W., T.M.N., and E.R.; and writing – review and editing, N.V., C.-W.H., Z.A., M.F., E.T., Y.Z., S.S.-G., K.W., T.M.N., and E.R.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

STAR★METHODS

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SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

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STAR★METHODS

KEY RESOURCES TABLE

REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Antibodies		
Mouse monoclonal HRP-conjugated anti-GFP antibody	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-091-833; RRID: AB_247003
Chicken polyclonal HRP-conjugated anti-HA antibody	Abcam	Cat# ab1190; RRID: AB_298683
Mouse anti-RFP antibody	ChromoTek	Cat# 6g6; RRID: AB_2631395
Mouse monoclonal anti-Tubulin antibody	Merck	Cat# T5168-100UL; RRID: AB_477579
Sheep Anti-Mouse IgG-HRP	Cytiva	Cat# NXA931; RRID: AB_772209
Bacterial and virus strains		
<i>E. coli</i> DH5a competent cell	Lab stock	N/A
<i>A. tumefaciens</i> C58C1	Lab stock	N/A
Chemicals, peptides, and recombinant proteins		
β-Estradiol	Sigma-Aldrich	E8875
Dexamethasone	Sigma-Aldrich	D4902
Bikinin	Sigma-Aldrich	SML0094
Brassinolide	OiChemIm, Ltd.	038 5891
Brassinazole	Tokyo Chemical Industry	B2829
MG132	Thermo Fisher Scientific	J63250.MCR
FM4-64	Thermo Fisher Scientific	T13320
GFP-Trap® Magnetic Agarose	ChromoTek	gtma
Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail PhosSTOP™	Merck	4906845001
EASYpack Protease Inhibitor Cocktail	Merck	5892791001
Quick Start™ Bradford 1x Dye Reagent	Bio-Rad	5000205
NuPAGE™ LDS Sample Buffer (4X)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	NP0008
NuPAGE™ Sample Reducing Agent (10X)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	NP0009
Skim milk	Thermo Fisher Scientific	11792994
Western Lightning Plus ECL reagent	Perkin Elmer	NEL104001EA
Critical commercial assays		
Gateway LR Clonase II Enzyme Mix	Invitrogen	11791020
Gateway BP Clonase II Enzyme Mix	Invitrogen	11789020
Mini-PROTEAN® TGX™ Precast Gels	Bio-Rad	4561096
Trans-Blot Turbo Mini 0.2 μm Nitrocellulose Transfer Pack	Bio-Rad	1704158
NEBuilder® HiFi DNA Assembly Master Mix	New England Biolabs	E2621L
Chromium X Single Cell Controller	10X Genomics	1000331
Dual Index Kit TT Set A	10X Genomics	1000215
Chromium Next GEM Single Cell 3' HT Kit v3.1	10X Genomics	1000348
Chromium Next GEM Chip M Single Cell Kit	10X Genomics	1000371
DNA High Sensitivity Bioanalyzer Kit	Agilent	Cat#5067-4626
Deposited data		
Single Cell mRNA Sequencing data	This paper	GEO: GSE262840
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_71	This paper	GEO: GSM8180251
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_157	This paper	GEO: GSM8180252
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_158	This paper	GEO: GSM8180253

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REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_159	This paper	GEO: GSM8180254
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_169	This paper	GEO: GSM8180255
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_170	This paper	GEO: GSM8180256
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_171	This paper	GEO: GSM8180257
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_215	This paper	GEO: GSM8180258
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_221	This paper	GEO: GSM8180260
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_229	This paper	GEO: GSM8180262
Single Cell RNA-Seq wild-type <i>Arabidopsis</i> root cells - sc_235	This paper	GEO: GSM8180263
Unprocessed blots	This paper	https://zenodo.org/records/14748834
Additional videos	This paper	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748704
Experimental models: Organisms/strains		
<i>Nicotiana benthamiana</i>	Lab stock	N/A
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> , wild-type (Col-0)	Lab stock	N/A
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> (MoneyMaker)	Lab stock	N/A
Col-0: pBZR1:BZR1-YFP	Wang et al. ⁴²	N/A
Col-0: pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP	Desvoves et al. ³⁵	N/A
Col-0: pCDT1a:CDT1a-GFP	Desvoves et al. ³⁵	N/A
Col-0: pUBQ10:BES1-Ypet/pUBQ10:H2B-mCherry/pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP	This paper	N/A
Col-0: pATSK11:ATSK11-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
Col-0: pATSK12:ATSK12-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
Col-0: pATSK13:ATSK13-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
Col-0: pATSK21:ATSK21-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
Col-0: pATSK22:ATSK22-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
Col-0: pATSK23:ATSK23-GFP	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
<i>dwf4</i> : pDWF4:DWF4-GFP	Vukašinović et al. ⁶	N/A
<i>cpd</i> : pCPD:CPD-GFP	Vukašinović et al. ⁶	N/A
<i>br6ox1/br6ox2</i> : pBR6OX2:GFP-BR6OX2	Vukašinović et al. ⁶	N/A
<i>dwf4</i> : pWER:DWF4-GFP	Vukašinović et al. ⁶	N/A
Col-0: pRPS5A:TMO5-GR/pRPS5A:LHW-GR (dGR)	Smet et al. ⁴⁷	N/A
pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/ <i>dwf4</i> : pRPS5A:TMO5-GR/pRPS5A:LHW-GR (dGR)	This paper	N/A
Col-0: pOPS:OPS-GFP	Truernit et al. ⁴⁸	N/A
Col-0: pOPL2:OPL2-GFP	Ruiz Sola et al. ⁸	N/A
<i>ops</i> : pOPS:OPL2-GFP	Ruiz Sola et al. ⁸	N/A
<i>ops/opl2</i>	Ruiz Sola et al. ⁸	N/A
<i>bri1</i> : pBRI1:BRI1-mCitrine	Jaillais et al. ⁶⁴	N/A
pBES1:BES1-GFP in Col-0	Jiang et al. ⁶⁵	N/A
Col-0: pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato	Zhou et al. ⁶⁶	N/A
Col-0: pATSK31:ATSK31-GFP	This paper	N/A
Col-0: pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP	This paper	N/A
Col-0: pATSK42:ATSK42-GFP	This paper	N/A

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REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
<i>pOPS:OPS-GFP; pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pOPL2:OPL2-GFP; pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP; pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pCDT1a:CDT1a-GFP; pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pBZR1:BZR1-YFP; pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP; pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; pRPS5a:mCherry-BASL</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; pRPS5a-XVE:BES1-D-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; pKN:BES1-D-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP; pOPL2:OPL2-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP; pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; p35S:OPL2-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP; p35S:OPL2-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pBZR1:BZR1-YFP; pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pOPS:OPS-GFP; pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pOPL2:OPL2-GFP; pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; pKN:ATSK32-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
PlaCCI	Desvoyes et al. ²¹	N/A
PlaCCI: <i>pAT5G06860:mNG</i>	This paper	N/A
PlaCCI: <i>pAT5G59690:mNG</i>	This paper	N/A
PlaCCI: <i>pAT5G16250:mNG</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato; pBZR1:BZR1-YFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato; pDWF4:DWF4-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
Col-0: <i>p35S:BES1-GFP</i>	De Rybel et al. ⁴³	N/A
Col-0: <i>p35S:BZR1-YFP</i>	Kim et al. ⁶⁷	N/A
Col-0: <i>pTMO5:TMO5-3GFP</i>	De Rybel et al. ⁶⁸	N/A
Col-0: <i>pLHW:LHW-YFP</i>	De Rybel et al. ⁶⁸	N/A
<i>pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dwf4; atsk31/atsk32 CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>bri1/br11/br3</i>	Irani et al. ⁶⁹	N/A
<i>bri1/br11/br3:PlaCCI</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>S. lycopersicum</i> (MoneyMaker): <i>pSICPD:gSICPD-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A

Oligonucleotides

See Table S2.

Recombinant DNA

<i>pK7m34GW - pATSK31:ATSK31-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pK7m34GW - pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pK7m34GW - pATSK42:ATSK42-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDONR P2r-P3 - BASL</i>	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - pRPS5a:mCherry-BASL</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - pRPS5a-XVE:BES1-D-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - pOPL2:OPL2-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - p35S:OPL2-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pK8m34GW-FAST - pRPS5a-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pDONRP4-P1r - pKNOLLE</i>	Marquès-Bueno et al. ⁷⁰	N/A
<i>pK8m34GW-FAST - pKN:ATSK32-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A

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REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
<i>pK8m34GW-FAST - pKN:BES1-D-mCherry</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pB7m24GW-FAST - pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato</i>	Wang et al. ⁷¹	N/A
<i>pDGB3_Q1 - PlaCCI</i>	Desvoyes et al. ²¹	N/A
<i>pK7FWG2 - p35S:POLAR-GFP</i>	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
<i>pK7m34GW - p35S:BIN2-HA</i>	Zhang et al. ⁷²	N/A
<i>pH8m34GW-FAST - p35S:OPL2-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pK7m34GW - p35S:ATSK32-HA</i>	Lu et al. ⁴⁴	N/A
<i>pK7FWG2 - p35S:GFP</i>	Houbaert et al. ⁶³	N/A
<i>FastRed-Kan-L1-Plant-pAT5G06860:mNeonGreen-NLS</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>FastRed-Kan-L1-Plant-pAT5G16250:mNeonGreen-NLS</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>FastRed-Kan-L1-Plant-pAT5G59690:mNeonGreen-NLS</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pGGK-A-G - pSICPD:gSICPD-GFP</i>	This paper	N/A
<i>pRPS5A:ATSK31-ATSK32-CRISPR</i>	This paper	N/A
Software and algorithms		
Image Lab software	Bio-Rad	https://www.bio-rad.com/en-be/product/image-lab-software
GraphPad prism9	GraphPad	https://www.graphpad.com/features
Inkscape	Open source	https://inkscape.org/
Imagej and Fiji	NIH	https://imagej.net/software/fiji/
scKB and COPILOT	Shahan et al. ¹⁶ ; Hsu et al. ⁷³	https://github.com/Hsu-Che-Wei/COPILOT
Seurat (v4.1.1.9001)	Hao et al. ¹⁸	https://satijalab.org/seurat/
tricycle (v1.6.0)	Zheng et al. ¹⁹	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/tricycle.html
ComplexHeatmap (v2.14.0)	Gu et al. ⁷⁴	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ComplexHeatmap.html
SingleCellExperiment (v1.20.0)	Amezquita et al. ⁷⁵	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/SingleCellExperiment.html
tradeSeq (v1.12.0)	Van den Berge et al. ⁷⁶	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/tradeSeq.html
WGCNA (v1.72-1)	Langfelder and Horvath ⁷⁷	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/WGCNA/index.html
GeneOverlap (v1.12.0)	http://shenlab-sinai.github.io/shenlab-sinai/	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/GeneOverlap.html
gprofiler2 (v0.2.2)	Kolberg et al. ⁷⁸	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/gprofiler2/index.html
MorphoGraphX 2.0	Strauss et al. ⁷⁹	https://morphographx.org/
MorphoDynamX	Strauss et al. ⁷⁹	https://morphographx.org/morphodynamx/
Root Model	This paper	https://github.com/WabnikLab/BR_ROOT_M

EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND STUDY PARTICIPANT DETAILS

Plant material and growth conditions

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh. Col-0 plants were used in all experiments. Seeds were surface-sterilized with the sterilization buffer (80% [v/v] ethanol, 20% [v/v] sodium hypochlorite), placed on half-strength Murashige and Skoog (½MS) agar plates and stratified for 2 days in the dark at 4 °C. Seedlings were grown vertically at 22°C, in a 16-h/8-h light/dark photoperiod.

Tomato *Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Ailsa Craig was used as the wild type genetic background. Seeds of wild type or the tomato T₁ transgenic line *SICPDpro:gSICPD-GFP* (see below) were surface sterilized in 70% (v/v) ethanol for 10 min followed by 50% (v/v) commercial bleach treatment for 20 min and three five-min washes with sterile deionized water. Seeds were plated on 12 cm x 12 cm plates containing 4.3 g l⁻¹ Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium (Duchefa M0221), 10 g l⁻¹ sucrose, 0.5 g l⁻¹ MES, pH 5.8 and 10 g l⁻¹ agar (Neogen NCM0250A), and maintained in a tissue culture room with 16 h of light at 24 °C and 8 h of darkness at 18 °C for 7-10 days. Root tips of only primary roots were used for confocal analysis.

METHOD DETAILS

Vector construction and generation of transgenic *Arabidopsis* lines

To generate *pATSK31:ATSK31-GFP*, *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP*, *pATSK42:ATSK42-GFP*, *pOPL2:OPL2-mCherry* and *pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry*, 2 kbp, 1.2 kbp, 1.1 kbp, 2.7 kbp and 1 kbp promoter regions upstream from the start codon for each gene, as well as full genomic coding sequences were amplified by PCR and cloned into *pDONRP4-P1R* for promoters and *pDONR221* for genomic sequences, using the Gateway BP clonase enzyme mix. ATSKs entry clones were combined with *pDONR-R2-eGFP-L3* and *pK7m34GW* vector and OPL2 and BZR1 clones with *pDONR-R2-mCherry-L3* and *pH8m34GW-FAST* destination vector in LR reaction to obtain expression clones. To generate *pRPS5a:mCherry-BASL* expression clone, entry clone *pDONR-R2-BASL-L3*, was combined with *pDONR-L4-pRPS5A-R1* and *pEN-L1-mCherryNoStop-L2* and *pH8m34GW-FAST* destination vectors in LR reaction. BES1-D and OPS coding sequences were amplified by PCR, cloned into *pDONR221*, and combined with *pDONR-L4-pRPS5A-XVE-R1* and *pDONR-R2-mCherry-L3* into *pH8m34GW-FAST* destination vector in LR reaction to obtain *pRPS5A-XVE:OPS-mCherry* and *pRPS5A-XVE:BES1-D-mCherry* constructs. To generate *p35s:OPL2-mCherry* and *p35s:OPL2-GFP* expression clones, full genomic OPL2 coding sequence was amplified by PCR and cloned into *pDONR221* and combined with *pDONR-L4-p35S-R1* and *pDONR-R2-mCherry-L3* or *pDONR-R2-GFP-L3* into *pH8m34GW-FAST* destination vector in LR reaction. To generate *pKN:ATSK32-mCherry* and *pKN:BES1-D-mCherry* expression clones, ATSK32 and BES1-D coding sequences were amplified by PCR, cloned into *pDONR221* and combined with *pDONR-L4-pKN-R1* and *pDONR-R2-mCherry-L3* into *pK8m34GW-FAST* destination vector in LR reaction. Expression clones were introduced into *Arabidopsis* plants using the floral-dip method.⁸⁰ *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* and *pATSK42:ATSK42-GFP* were introduced into Col-0 background. *pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry* construct was introduced into *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP*, *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP*, *pOPS:OPS-GFP*, *pOPL2:OPL2-GFP* and *pCDT1a:CDT1a-GFP* reporter lines. *pRPS5A-XVE:OPS-mCherry* and *pOPL2:OPL2-mCherry* were introduced into *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP*. *p35s:OPL2-mCherry* construct was introduced into *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* and *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP*. *pRPS5a:mCherry-BASL*, *pRPS5A-XVE:BES1-D-mCherry*, *pKN:ATSK32-mCherry* and *pKN:BES1-D-mCherry* were introduced into *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP*. *PlaCCI* was introduced into *bri1/bri1/bri3*.

To facilitate the one-step generation of new reporters for cell cycle marker genes, we adapted a cloning strategy as previously described.²⁵ We used a BsaI golden gate reaction to assemble a PaqCI flanked RFP dropout upstream of a nuclear reporter, UbiNeonGreen-N7,⁸¹ followed by the Ubiquitin10 terminator (tUBQ10). TN407 FASTRED backbone based on pICH86966 (Addgene plasmid #48075) was used as a MoClo Level 1 acceptor for these constructs. Approximately 3 kbp upstream promoter sequences for *AT5G06860*, *AT5G59690*, or *AT5G16250* were amplified using primers containing flanking PaqCI sites and combined with the *PaqCI-RFP-dropout-PaqCI:UbiNeonGreen-N7-tUBQ10* backbone in a golden gate reaction. This resulted in a *Promoter:UbiNeonGreen-N7-tUBQ10* construct. Following full-length plasmid sequencing, the constructs were introduced into the Plant Cell Cycle Indicator (PlaCCI) background.²¹ *pRPS5A-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* construct was generated using the previously described cloning method.^{25,82} Three gRNAs targeting *OPS* were introduced into gRNA expression cassettes *pGG-A-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-B*, *pGG-B-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-C* and *pGG-C-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-D* and three gRNAs targeting *OPL2* were introduced into *pGG-D-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-E*, *pGG-E-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-F* and *pGG-F-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-G*. Next, gRNA modules were combined into *pEN-R2-A-G-L3* by restriction-ligation using BsaI enzyme (New England Biolabs) to obtain *pEN-R2-gRNA-OPS-1_gRNA-OPS-2_gRNA-OPS-3_gRNA-OPL2-1_gRNA-OPL2-2_gRNA-OPL2-3-L3*. This plasmid was combined with *pDONR-L1-Cas9p-tagRFP-L2*,⁸³ *pDONR-L4-pRPS5A-XVE-R1* and a destination vector *pK8m34GW-FAST* in LR reaction to obtain expression clones. *pRPS5A-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* construct was introduced into *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP*, *pOPS:OPS-GFP* and *pOPL2:OPL2-GFP* reporter lines using the floral dip method. To generate *atsk31/atsk32* double CRISPR mutant, two gRNAs targeting *ATSK32* were introduced into gRNA expression cassettes *pGG-A-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-B* and *pGG-B-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-C* and four gRNAs targeting *ATSK31* were introduced into gRNA expression cassettes *pGG-C-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-D*, *pGG-D-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-E*, *pGG-E-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-F* and *pGG-F-AtU6-26-BbsI-ccdB-BbsI-G*. Entry vectors were assembled in the destination vector *pFASTRK-RPS5AP-AtCas9-NLS-P2A-mCherry-G7T-A-CmR-ccdB-G* via Golden Gate assembly,⁸² resulting in the construct *pRPS5A:ATSK31-ATSK32-CRISPR*. This construct was introduced into *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* reporter line. Mutations in *ATSK31* and *ATSK32* genes were sequence-verified. *ATSK31* sequence contains two single nucleotide insertions at the positions 274 (A) and 463 (T) and 22 nucleotide deletion at the position 944-965 from the start codon of the genomic sequence. *ATSK32* sequence contains a single nucleotide insertion (A) at the position 577 from the start codon of the genomic sequence. Cloning primers and gRNA sequences are listed in [Table S2](#).

pUBQ10:BES1-Ypet/pUBQ10:H2B-mCherry was crossed with *pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP*, *dGR* was crossed with *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP*, *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* was crossed with *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato*, *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* was crossed with *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato*, and *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* were crossed with *pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato*.

Validation of inducible CRISPR lines

We tested the functionality of the *pRPS5A-XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* double knockout construct by introducing it into *pOPS:OPS-GFP* and *pOPL2:OPL2-GFP* lines, respectively. We monitored disappearance of the GFP signal as an indicator of a gene knockout. After 20 h of induction on estradiol, the GFP signal was almost completely absent in both transgenic lines. This coincided with appearance of Cas9-RFP signal, indicating an efficient knockout ([Figure S7B](#)). Next, we introduced *XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* into the *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* line and compared it with *ops/opl2* double mutant. After long term, 9-day induction on estradiol inducible

CRISPR line displayed similar phenotypic defects compared to *ops/op2* double mutant, indicating again an efficient knockout (Figure S7C).

Cloning of the tomato CPD gene and generation of transgenic tomato lines

Our previous study shows that *Arabidopsis* CPD (AT5G05690) fused C-terminally with a GFP is functional.⁶ The cultivated tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) genome encodes only one CPD gene by Solyc06g051750 (International Tomato Genome Sequencing Project, ITAG4.0). We constructed the vector p*SICPD:gSICPD-GFP* where the native promoter drives the expression of *SICPD* tagged with a C-terminal GFP using the Golden Gate cloning method as previously described.⁸² Briefly, the native promoter (2930 bp from the start codon) and the coding region (6752 bp without stop codon) of *SICPD* were PCR amplified from tomato genomic DNA (*cv.* MoneyMaker) using gene-specific oligonucleotides (Table S2). The gel purified PCR products were inserted into Bsal-linearized Golden Gate entry vectors via Gibson assembly using 2× NEBuilder HiFi DNA Assembly Mix (New England Biolabs), generating two vectors pGG-A-*SICPDpro-B* and pGG-C-*gSICPD-D*. The Golden Gate entry modules pGG-A-*SICPDpro-B*, pGG-B-Linker-C, pGG-C-*gSICPD-D*, pGG-D-GFP-E, pGG-E-35ST-F and pGG-F-LinkerII-G were assembled in the destination vector pGGK-A-G via Golden Gate assembly,⁸² resulting in the construct p*SICPD:gSICPD-GFP*.

The recombinant binary vector p*SICPD:gSICPD-GFP* was introduced into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain GV3101 and transformed into tomato (*S. lycopersicum cv.* Ailsa Craig) using the tomato cotyledon transformation method described previously.⁸⁴ Briefly, explants of cotyledons were excised from the 7-day-old *in vitro* grown tomato seedling and cut near the petiole and tip, placed on a plate containing appropriate co-cultivation media, and preincubated for 24 h at room temperature under dark conditions. Co-cultivation of excised explants with agrobacterium (OD600 = 0.4) was carried out for 48 h under dark conditions. After co-cultivation, explants were transferred to shoot induction medium containing zeatin (1.75 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), indole-3-acetic acid (1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and ticarcillin (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for 3-4 weeks under 26 °C (16 h day)/18 °C (8 h night), and then transferred to shoot elongation medium containing zeatin riboside (0.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), indole-3-acetic acid (0.01 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and ticarcillin (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for another 2-3 weeks. Subsequently, well-developed shoots were excised and transferred to rooting medium containing indole-3-butyric acid (2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and ticarcillin (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). After 3 to 4 weeks, plantlets with roots were transferred to soils in greenhouse and maintained for further analysis. Transgene-positive T0 plants were identified by Phire plant direct PCR kit (Thermo Scientific) using a pair of genotyping oligonucleotides (Table S2). The GFP signal was confirmed in T₁ plants under confocal microscopy.

Microscopy

Seedlings for imaging on vertical microscope setup were grown on ½ MS agar plates for 5 to 7 days, transferred to fresh agar slabs, placed in imaging chambers (Nunc™ Lab-Tek™ II Chambered Coverglass, Thermo Fisher Scientific), sealed with surgical tape and imaged immediately. Imaging of root apical meristems was performed using a vertical ZEISS LSM900 microscope equipped with a Plan-Apochromat M27 20×/0.8 n.a. Multiple root tips were tracked over time (up to 48 h) with the TipTracker software.³⁴ Usually, 6 to 8 roots were placed in the chamber for a single experiment. In cases when mutant line was compared with the wild-type or inducible line with the mock, 3 or 4 seedlings of each group were grown side by side in the same chamber. Imaging was performed in the dark, unless stated otherwise in description of the experiment. For long-term imaging interval was from 10 to 15 min. Number of Z-stacks (3 μm interval) used was from 14 to 20. For high temporal imaging, intervals were 1 min long and up to 10 Z-stacks (2 μm interval) were imaged. The excitation/emission wavelengths were the following: GFP, YFP, mCitrine and mNeonGreen 488/490-545, tdTomato, RFP and mCherry 561/565-617 and CFP 405/410-524.

Imaging of p*UBQ10:BES1-Ypet/pUBQ10:H2B-mCherry/pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP* line. Four-day-old seedlings were transferred to ibidi chambered coverslip (μ -Slide 1 Well Glass Bottom, Cat.No:82107). A thin slab (3-4 mm) of 0.5 MS medium supplemented with 1 % agar was placed on top of the seedlings, excluding the aerial part. The lid was then fixed with micropore tape of 3M Micropore™ to retain moisture in the chambered coverslip. The chambered coverslip was placed vertically in the plant growth chamber for overnight to acclimate the seedlings before imaging. For imaging of BES1-Ypet/H2B-mCherry/CDT1a-CFP, fluorescent signals were detected using an inverted microscope (Nikon ECLIPSE Ti2-Eclipse) attached with a spinning disc confocal unit (Yokogawa CSU-W1). Ypet was excited at 488 nm and emission was acquired with a 525/50 nm filter, mCHERRY was excited at 561 nm and emission was acquired with a 600/52 nm filter, eCFP was excited at 405 nm and emission was acquired with a 525/50 nm filter. Pixels were binned 2x2 to improve signal brightness. A high-resolution imaging was carried out with a X60 water immersion objective lens (Plan Apo VC 60x/NA WI DIC N2, Numerical aperture = 1.2). Plants were imaged for a total of 4 hours with 10 min intervals. Confocal stacks spanning the epidermis (~17 μm distributed in 21 slices of 0.8 μm interval) were acquired at each time point. For long-term imaging of roots conducted with a ×20 objective lens (S Plan Fluor LWD 20xC, Numerical aperture = 0.7), plants were imaged for a duration of 10.5 h with 15 min intervals. A motorized stage of Ti2-E was attached and controlled by the NIS-elements software (Nikon Solutions) with the 'Keep object in view' plug-in to automatically track root meristems. Tracking of the root meristem, multi-point image acquisition was controlled by the Nikon NIS-elements platform integrated with Jobs plug-in. To ensure precise tracking of the root meristem, 2D mCherry images were taken in intervals of 7.5 min. Confocal stacks spanning the epidermis (40 μm distributed in 40 slices of 1 μm interval) were acquired at each time point. No photobleaching was detected using these imaging settings over the course of the experiment.

Image analysis and Quantification

Individual LSM files acquired at vertical ZEISS LSM900 microscope were converted into hyperstacks using a Fiji macro.³⁴ Hyperstacks were then used to produce maximum intensity projection time-lapse videos or single Z-stack time-lapse videos by manually stabilizing a single root section. Hyperstacks were also used to label ROIs for fluorescence intensity quantifications as well as to determine the duration of the cell cycle, by manually tracking single cells from the moment of their birth until the next cell division.

To quantify BZR1-YFP and DWF4-GFP signal, we crossed *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* with a plasma membrane marker line *pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato*. This allowed automatic cell segmentation using the membrane signal. We measured the gene expression level in the dividing cells using the following procedure. First, Cellpose⁸⁵ was used to segment root cells with parameters “pretrained_model: cytorch_0, diameter: 25”. Next, we removed cells with sizes smaller than 200 px, and used the scikit-image toolkit⁸⁶ to align adjacent frames with optical flow registration (optical flow was generated with iterative Lucas-Kanade solver, and further polished by fitting into a linear gradient before registration) for tracking cells. When the intersection area of a cell and another cell in the next aligned frame was greater than half the union area, these cells were tracked as continuous cells in different frames. When multiple cells had an intersection area of a parent cell in the previous frame greater than half of their respective area, they were assigned to be divided from the same parent cell. The aligned frames were only used for cell tracking, and signal quantification was done on un-aligned images. The BZR1-YFP signal was used to segment the cell nucleus. The signal was denoised with a median filter before Otsu thresholding. Hole removal and binary closing were used to further polish the cell nucleus area. For each cell division event, we tracked the parent cell for about 12-15 frames and the daughter cells for about 25-30. For each tracked cell, we measured the mean intensity in the nucleus (for BZR1-YFP) or the whole cell (for DWF4-GFP) for each frame. For samples without plasma membrane markers, dividing cells were manually marked with a bounding box in Fiji. The nuclei were segmented in marked cells with CellPose, the parameters of which were manually checked and optimized in each image for correct segmentation. The mean intensity in the nucleus area was used for further quantification. For statistical analysis, we aligned all cell division events using the cell division frame as frame 0 and trimmed them to the same length. We used the intensity in the first frame of each event as the reference intensity to normalize the intensity levels in each event by \log_2 fold change. The confidence interval was calculated with the *scipy* package (*scipy.stats.interval*), with the confidence threshold set to 0.95.

The number of cell division events and roots analyzed for each line is listed below: *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* in *pUBQ10:RCI2a-tdTomato* (48 cell division events from 4 roots); *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* in *pUBQ10:RCI2a-tdTomato* (20 cell division events from 3 roots); *p35S:BES1-GFP* (18 cell division events from 2 roots); *p35S:BZR1-YFP* (22 cell division events from 4 roots); *p35S:BZR1-YFP + MG132* (24 cell division events from 3 roots); *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* in *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato* (28 cell division events from 4 roots); *pAT-SK32:ATSK32-GFP* in *pH3.3:NLS-tdTomato* (37 cell division events from 3 roots). *pBZR1:BZR1-mCherry* in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* quantification was performed manually (18 cell division events from 4 roots). To score the number of cell division events in which BR signaling displays differences between upper and lower daughter cells *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* in *pUBQ10:RCI2a-tdTomato* line was analyzed. BZR1-YFP nuclear signal was quantified at single time frame around 120 min after cell division. 152 cell division events from 4 roots were analyzed. To quantify DWF4-GFP signal in daughter cells after radial and anticlinal cell divisions in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP/dGR* line, a single time frame (180 min after cell division) with the highest DWF4-GFP was chosen for analysis. 22 radial and 25 anticlinal cell division events from 5 roots were analyzed. To quantify cytoplasmic OPL2-GFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells after anticlinal cell divisions, a single time frame at 100 min after cell division was chosen for analysis. The same area size of cytoplasm was compared between sister cells. 25 epidermal and 25 cortical cell division events from 3 roots were analyzed.

For *pUBQ10:BES1-Ypet/pUBQ10:H2B-mCherry/pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP* line imaging, nuclear signal intensities of the Ypet, mCherry, and eCFP channels were obtained from the spinning disc confocal images with Imaris software (Imaris 10.0), using the Spot Detection and Tracking module. To determine the Ypet/mCherry ratio, we first extracted the nuclear signal intensity of Ypet in individual cells and then divided this value by the corresponding nuclear signal intensity of mCherry in the same cell. For the calculation of eCFP/mCherry ratio, all images of eCFP and mCherry underwent background subtraction with Imaris (10 μ m filter). Then, the eCFP/mCherry ratio was calculated similarly to the calculation of the Ypet/mCherry ratio. Next, the eCFP/mCherry ratio was normalized to fit its values with the ones of Ypet/mCherry on the same graph. This normalization was performed by dividing the eCFP/mCherry ratio by the average of eCFP/mCherry ratio observed in a specific cell division event. Epidermal meristematic cells up to 100 μ m from the QC were measured, in 16 independent division events in 4 distinct roots.

Förster resonance energy transfer by fluorescence lifetime imaging (FRET-FLIM) analysis

pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP and *XVE:OPS-mCherry* in *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* lines were grown for 4 days and then transferred to media containing 10 μ M estradiol for 36 h. For imaging, plants were mounted to a stage of Zeiss LSM880 (Carl Zeiss) equipped with an apochromatic 40 \times /1.2 objective. For GFP, the fluorescence was excited with 930 nm wavelength by a multi-photon laser Chameleon Ultra II (Coherent) and a 525/50 filter. For mCherry, 561 nm Laser 20 mW was used. To record fluorescence lifetimes, we used a FLIM module equipped with a Becker-Hickl card SPC-150 (Becker & Hickl GmbH), a hybrid detector for Time-Correlated Single-Photon Counting (TCSPC, Becker & Hickl GmbH) and SPCM64 data acquisition software (Becker & Hickl GmbH). The lifetime of GFP was measured in regions of interest (ROIs) in the cytoplasm or plasma membrane. The values were fitted to an incomplete multi-exponential decay model using the SPCImagev8.5 software (Becker & Hickl GmbH). The lifetime was recorded at approximately 4-5 min per image. The mean lifetime of each ROI is shown.

Immunoblot analysis

pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP and *XVE:OPS-mCherry* in *pATSK32:ATSK32-GFP* lines were grown for 5 days and then transferred to liquid ½ MS media containing 10 μM estradiol for 10 h. Around 20 mg of frozen plant tissue (whole seedlings) per sample was flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and pulverized. Total proteins were extracted with extraction buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 0.5% (v/v) Triton X-100, 10% (v/v) glycerol, complete EDTA-free protease inhibitor cocktail and phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (PhosSTOP) on ice for 30 min. The extracts were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 20 min, and the total protein concentrations in the supernatants were determined with the Quick Start™ Bradford 1x Dye Reagent. Equal amounts of 25 μg proteins were mixed with 4x NuPAGE LDS Sample Buffer to a final concentration of 1x with 50 mM dithiothreitol (DTT; NuPAGE Sample Reducing Agent) and denatured at 70 °C for 10 min. Proteins were loaded to 4–20% precast SDS-PAGE gel, separated with Mini-PROTEAN Tetra Vertical Electrophoresis Cell (Bio-Rad), and transferred onto 0.2 μm nitrocellulose membranes using the Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (Bio-Rad) by following the manufacturer's instructions. Subsequently, the nitrocellulose membranes were blocked with PBST buffer (PBS plus 0.1% (v/v) Tween 20) containing 5% (w/v) skim milk at room temperature for 1 h. The membranes were incubated with the corresponding antibodies diluted in PBST buffer with 1% (w/v) skim milk. To detect ATSK32-GFP, the primary antibody in conjugation to horseradish peroxidase (HRP) against GFP (1:2,000 dilution) was incubated at room temperature for 1 h. Tubulin was used as the endogenous control. Primary mouse anti-tubulin antibody (1:5,000 dilution) was incubated at room temperature for 1 h. To probe OPS-mCherry, the mouse anti-RFP primary antibody (1:1,000 dilution) was incubated at 4 °C overnight. HRP-conjugated anti-mouse IgG secondary antibody (1:10,000 dilution) was applied to incubate with the membranes at room temperature for 1 h. After washing in PBST, signal detection was performed using Western Lightning Plus ECL reagent and captured using the ChemiDoc Imaging System equipped with the Image Lab software (Bio-Rad). Absolute band intensities with background subtractions were measured with ImageJ to represent protein levels. The value of ATSK32-GFP in each sample was divided to that of α-Tubulin for normalization and those ratios were used in statistical analysis. Unprocessed blots are available at Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/14748834>.

Co-immunoprecipitation (co-IP) assay

Agrobacterium strain C58C1, containing the constructs of interest, along with a strain harboring p19, was co-infiltrated into the abaxial side of tobacco (*N. benthamiana*) leaves following the previously described method.⁸⁷ Infiltrated leaves were observed 3–4 days after infiltration to verify expression using confocal microscopy. Samples were then collected and frozen in liquid nitrogen prior to processing. The samples were prepared by grinding between 0.3 and 1 g of leaf material. Extraction buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 10% glycerol, 1 mM EDTA, 0.5% Triton X-100, protease inhibitor, 10 μM MG132, 1 mM PMSF, 10 mM DTT) was added to the freshly powderized tissue and the samples are allowed to thaw on ice. The sample was then collected and centrifuged 3 times at >13,000 RPM at <5 °C for 10 min, ensuring to transfer no sediment between centrifugations. After clearing, 25 μl of α-GFP magnetic beads were added to 750 μl of sample extract and incubated for 2 hours on a rotating wheel at 4 °C. The beads were collected using a magnetic rack and washed three times with 1 ml of wash buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM EDTA, 0.5% Triton X-100). The proteins were eluted from the beads by adding a modified LDS sample buffer (LDS Sample Buffer (4X), Sample Reducing Agent (10X), 10%–15% SDS) and boiled for 10 minutes at 90 °C. Protein samples were separated by 4–20% TGX protein gels, transferred, and the membrane was analyzed separately with an α-GFP HRP-conjugated antibody (mouse monoclonal 1:5,000) for GFP-tagged proteins and an α-HA HRP-conjugated antibody (polyclonal anti-chicken 1:5000) for HA-tagged proteins. Unprocessed blots are available at Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/14748834>.

Chemical treatments

The following chemicals were used for treatments in this study: brassinolide (OChemIm, Ltd.), brassinazole (Tokyo Chemical Industry), β-estradiol (Sigma-Aldrich), dexamethasone (Sigma-Aldrich) and bikinin (Sigma-Aldrich). All chemicals were kept at desired stock concentrations in DMSO and diluted 1,000×, except for bikinin (715x) to reach final concentrations in the medium.

Root growth model description

The model was built using MorphoDynamX, a computer modelling platform based on MorphoGraphX.⁸⁸ MorphoDynamX involves advanced computations based on a geometric data structure called Cell Complexes.⁸⁹ The mechanical growth of the simulated root is based on Position-Based Dynamics (PBD), a constraint-based method used to simulate physical phenomena like cloth, deformation, fluids, fractures, rigidity, etc.⁹⁰ Biochemical species are numerically solved using the explicit Euler method. The current model builds on previous modeling framework integrating cell growth mechanics with biochemical simulations.⁵⁴ Since brassinosteroid signaling and brassinosteroid biosynthesis are mutually exclusive (as observed in our experiments and reported in literature), the model suggests that after cell division, at least one daughter cell produces a major pool of brassinosteroids. These brassinosteroid molecules then diffuse to the neighboring non-dividing cells, following the given formula:

$$\frac{dBRlev_i}{dt} = b_{BR} + PBR + D_{BR} \sum_j^m \frac{L_j}{A_i} \cdot (BRlev_j - BRlev_i) - d_{BR} \cdot BRlev_i$$

$$\frac{dPBR}{dt} = p_{BR}$$

BR_{lev_i} is brassinosteroids concentration in the i th cell. b_{BR} is a small leaky brassinosteroid basal production rate. PBR denotes a kinetics of post-division triggered brassinosteroid biosynthesis. p_{BR} is post-division brassinosteroid production rate in daughter cells. D_{BR} is brassinosteroid diffusions rate in adjacent cells. A_i is the total area of the i -th cell; the summation symbol indicates iteration over the (m) neighbor cells of the i -th cell, while BR_{lev_j} indicates brassinosteroid concentration in j -th neighbor. L_i is the length of the membrane compartment between the i -th cell and the j -th cell. d_{BR} is a brassinosteroid degradation rate.

Brassinosteroid signaling occurs in all growing/non-dividing cells and it controls the cell growth rate as follows:

$$\frac{dBRsig_i}{dt} = r_{BS}; \text{ if } BRsig_i < 1, \text{ otherwise } 1 \text{ in non - dividing cells}$$

$$\frac{dR_e}{dt} = Max_r(BR_{lev_i} * BRsig_i) \frac{(L_e - R_e)}{R_e}$$

$BRsig_i$ is brassinosteroid signaling level in the i th cell. R_e is the resting length of a given edge e making part of the cell membrane. Max_r is the maximum resting length update rate. L_e is the length of a given i th cell edge e . Since the experimental evidence indicates that ATSKs enter the nucleus prior to and during mitosis, likely resulting in a significant decrease of brassinosteroid signaling. This effect was incorporated into the model by setting BR signaling ($BRsig_i$) in i th daughter cell to zero immediately after cell division. The brassinosteroid signaling recovery is delayed (short or long delay) after cell division following the kinetic rate r_{BS} .

Since the model parameters could not be determined experimentally, we explored possible values by running hundreds of parallel simulations on the supercomputing cluster. This involved leveraging the extensive parallelization capabilities of GPU-powered MorphoDynamX platform to perform an initial calibration of parameters, aiming to align the model with previous reports that a ~ 15 % reduction in cell length and a 33 % reduction in cell division rates occurs in the BR biosynthetic mutant *dwf4*.⁶ In addition, we performed direct measurements of cell cycle duration in root epidermal cells of the *bri1/brl1/brl3* triple brassinosteroid receptor mutant using long-term confocal microscopy. We found around 20 % reduction of the cell cycle duration (Figures S7G and S7H). The values of the used parameters were as follows: $b_{BR} = 0.01$ (1/h), $D_{BR} = 1$ ($\mu\text{m}^2/\text{h}$), $d_{BR} = 0.1$ (1/h), $p_{BR} = 1$ (1/h), $r_{BS} = 0.01$, $Max_r = 100$ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{h}$).

Following this initial calibration, we tested a root model for the robust growth by investigating a balance between brassinosteroid biosynthesis and signaling recovery after cell division. The following reasoning was applied to devise possible cellular scenarios after divisions. Central to the model is our observation that ATSKs enter the nucleus prior to and during mitosis, which we assume strongly decreases brassinosteroid signaling. In the computational model, we use an idealistic situation where signaling is set to zero immediately after division in both daughter cells. Next assumption, based on our experimental data is that the signaling rapidly recovers in daughter cells and there are three possible ways to do so - signaling will either recover equally in both cells (Scenario 2), more quickly in the upper cell (Scenario 3 UP) or more quickly in the lower cell (Scenario 3 LOW). For each of these scenarios we tested the importance of the time delay, with turned out to play a major role in root growth simulations.

scRNA-seq of *Arabidopsis* root protoplasts

Single-cell profiling of *Arabidopsis* root protoplasts was performed using 10X genomics 3' scRNA-seq as previously described.^{16,25} The plants were grown vertically in a growth chamber at 22 °C with a 16-hour light/8-hour dark cycle for five to seven days (listed for each sample in Table S1) on 1/2 Linsmaier and Skoog medium (LSP03-1LT, Caisson Labs; pH 5.7) containing 1% sucrose and covered with 100 μm nylon mesh (Nitex 03-100/44). Root tips were harvested from 1,000 to 3,000 roots per sample by cutting roughly 0.2-0.5 cm from the tip using a razor blade. The excised root tips were placed in a 35 mm petri dish containing a 70 μm cell strainer and 4.5 mL enzyme solution (1.5% [w/v] cellulase [ONOZUKA R-10, GoldBio], 0.1% Pectolyase [Sigma P3026], 0.4 M mannitol, 20 mM MES [pH 5.7], 20 mM KCl, 10 mM CaCl₂, 0.1% bovine serum albumin, and 0.000194% [v/v] beta-mercaptoethanol). The digestion was incubated on a shaker at 85 rpm at 25 °C for one hour, with occasional stirring every 15-20 minutes. Afterward, the cell suspension was filtered twice through 40 μm cell strainers and centrifuged at 500 g for five minutes using a swinging bucket rotor. The pellet was washed with 2 mL washing solution (0.4 M mannitol, 20 mM MES [pH 5.7], 20 mM KCl, 10 mM CaCl₂, 0.1 % bovine serum albumin, and 0.000194 % [v/v] beta-mercaptoethanol), centrifuged again for 3 minutes at 500 g, and then resuspended in the washing solution at approximately 2,000 cells/ μL .

A total of 32,000 cells were loaded, aiming to capture 20,000 cells per sample using the 10X Genomics Chromium 3' High-throughput Gene Expression v3.1 kits. Cell barcoding and library construction were performed according to the manufacturer's protocols. The cDNA and final library quality were validated using a Bioanalyzer High Sensitivity DNA Chip (Agilent) and sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 system.

Single-cell data processing

Sequencing reads were demultiplexed from Illumina BCL files to produce FASTQ files for each sample using CellRanger mkfastq (v3.1.0, 10X Genomics). FASTQ files were processed and quality-filtered using the scKB-COPILOT pipeline,⁷³ as demonstrated in

our previous publications.^{16,25} Cell type and developmental stage annotations were then transferred to samples from the root atlas (GEO:GSE152766) with updates to proliferation domain and transition domain annotations.²⁵ Code demonstrating this and each of the processes below are available on GitHub at https://github.com/tmnolan/Brassinosteroid_cell_cycle.

Cell cycle reference

A cell cycle reference was constructed by integrating 18 WT samples (Table S1) enriched in meristem cells (at least 300 proliferation domain cells) with only the cell cycle-associated genes. These cell cycle genes were compiled from three sources: *i*) Genes associated with the cell cycle GO term (GO:0007049) from AmiGO 2 (<https://amigo.geneontology.org/amigo>), *ii*) Genes published in Goldy et al., characterizing transcription factors and genes that control the cell cycle in the root,⁹¹ and *iii*) Genes published in Zhang et al., inferring the cell cycle genes in the shoot apex.¹⁵ For each sample to be integrated as the tricycle reference, we conducted differential analysis to identify cell-type specific genes with Seurat FindAllMarkers. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test was performed on SCTransformed assay for FindAllMarkers. Only the positive markers with adjusted p-value lower than 0.01 and the averaged fold change (\log_2) higher than 0.25 were considered as cell-type-specific genes. Next, we identified genes that were enriched in specific developmental stage by estimating z-scores of gene expression. Genes having the highest z-scores in elongation, maturation zones or the distal root cap were considered enriched in cells inactive in the cell cycle. We removed cell cycle-associated genes that were differentially expressed among cell types, enriched in the elongation zone/maturation zone/distal root cap, and those known to be induced by protoplasting. As a result, 199,810 cells were integrated with 245 cell cycle-associated genes (Table S1) using Seurat v4.¹⁸ The detailed code for the process can be found in the notebook “Ref_tricycle_20230823-Goldy_Zhang_GO” on GitHub.

Cell cycle position inference and phase annotation

The relative position of cell cycle progression was inferred on the cell cycle reference with principle component analysis (PCA) embeddings using the R package tricycle v1.6.0¹⁹ (Figure S1A). Three major cell populations can be observed on a cell density plot along the axis of cell cycle progression (Figure S1A). After intersecting the differentially expressed genes specific to each cell population with the known cell cycle phase markers,¹⁵ we determined that the three populations represent the three major cell cycle states (G1, S, G2/M) in the cell cycle-associated transcriptional landscape. Based on the cell density plot and the identity of each cell population (Figure S1A), we established position boundaries for each state as follows: G1 (0-1 pi), S (1-1.55 pi), G2/M (1.55-2 pi). Utilizing the established cell cycle reference and the defined phase boundaries, cells in all samples involved in this study were assigned a cell cycle position value and a corresponding phase annotation through the transfer learning functionality of the tricycle package.

Cell cycle phase marker identification

After inferring cell cycle position and annotating cell cycle phases, the same 18 WT samples comprising the cell cycle reference were integrated once again. However, this time, integration was performed with all other genes, except for protoplasting-induced genes. Only cells belonging to the proliferation domain and proximal root cap—where the cell cycle is most active—were selected. We then investigated the expression of three cell cycle phase markers that have been experimentally validated: G1 (AT5G21940), S (AT5G10390), and G2/M (AT4G23800)²⁰ (Figure S1B). To observe gene expression along the cell cycle progression, loess (locally weighted scatterplot smoothing) lines were fitted for the gene’s normalized expression along the axis of cell cycle position. As shown in Figure S1B, the expression of the markers aligns well with our tricycle inference. To search for additional cell cycle phase markers, we performed a differential expression analysis using FindMarkers in Seurat and gene co-expression analysis of our cell cycle-annotated single-cell data. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum test was performed on SCTransformed assay for FindMarkers to identify cell cycle phase specific markers. Only the positive markers with adjusted p-value lower than 0.01 and the averaged fold change (\log_2) higher than 0.25 were selected. The marker lists were ranked by averaged fold change (\log_2) and the cell type specificity was manually checked by plotting cell-type-specific gene expression along the cell cycle progression. We selected genes specific to each cell cycle phase but not enriched in particular cell types as potential cell cycle markers: G1 (AT5G06860), S (AT5G59690), and G2/M (AT5G16250), which were validated by the fluorescent reporter lines (Figures S1C–S1F). The detailed code for the process can be found in the notebook “Tricycle_18S_proliferation_proximal_cells_all_genes_20230907” on GitHub.

Identification of gene modules along cell cycle progression

To cluster patterns of gene expression along cell cycle pseudotime, a loess line was fitted for each gene’s normalized expression along the axis of the cell cycle position using only cells of the proliferation domain. We repurposed the Weighted Gene Correlation Network Analysis (WGCNA)⁷⁷ to identify gene modules that share a similar expression pattern along the cell cycle progression (parameters: power = 30, minModuleSize = 200 for signed network). Ten gene modules that exhibit distinct expression patterns along the cell cycle were identified. We removed modules that did not have significantly associated gene (significance level < 0.01) ontology terms, after which we labeled the gene modules based on the cell cycle phase during which the genes display elevated expression levels (Figure 1E).

Identification of cell cycle-dependent BR regulated genes

We used the GeneOverlap R package (version 1.12.0; <http://shenlab-sinai.github.io/shenlab-sinai/>) to intersect the brassinosteroid-regulated genes reported in our previous scRNA-seq analysis of brassinosteroid response in *Arabidopsis* roots²⁵ with the gene

modules identified in proliferation domain atrichoblasts. After Fisher's exact tests to examine the statistical significance of these gene list intersections, we observed that the brassinosteroid-regulated genes are enriched in the G1-Module 2.

Annotation of upper and lower daughter cells

We applied the same WGCNA analysis to the phloem atlas.⁵³ The atlas contains 10,204 cells including phloem, pericycle and other stele cell types. We performed label transfer of developmental zone annotation as previously described²⁵ to the phloem atlas, and selected the proliferation domain cells having phloem atlas label "CC", "dividing", "early PSE", "early/undetermined", "MSE", or "PSE". We used the resulting 3,645 proliferation domain phloem cells from the phloem atlas for WGCNA analysis, identifying gene modules and cell cycle-dependent brassinosteroid regulated genes. Based on the observation that upper daughter cells display increased BZR1 and BES1 transcription factor levels, while the lower daughter cells showed increased levels of brassinosteroid biosynthesis enzymes after cell division, we used BES1 and BZR1 target genes that are up-regulated upon brassinosteroid treatment and peaked in G1-Module 2 to annotate the upper cells and three brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes (CPD, DWF4 and CYP90D1) to annotate the lower cells. We calculated the mean of gene z-scores across cells that are annotated as G1 phase and annotated cells by comparing the z-score means. We selected the top 10% of cells based on the z-score mean for brassinosteroid up-regulated signal and brassinosteroid synthesis signal, and annotated them as putative "upper" and "lower" daughter cells respectively. Through differential expression analysis implemented in Seurat FindMarkers using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test,¹⁸ we identified potential markers representing the upper and lower cells, revealing that the upper cells are associated with cell wall functionalities based on GO analysis using the R package gprofiler2.⁷⁸

Annotation of mitotic and endocycle cells

To differentiate between mitotic and endocycle cells we took advantage of both marker genes and ploidy annotations. We calculated the mean of gene z-scores across cells and annotated cells by comparing the z-score means. The markers used for annotating mitotic cycle cells were *KNOLLE* (AT1G08560), *CSLD5* (AT1G02730), and *HINKEL* (AT1G18370). For endocycle cells, *SIM* (AT5G04470), *SMR1* (AT3G10525), and *CDC6* (AT2G29680)⁹² were used. To aid the annotation process, additional ploidy markers were used.^{16,93} We first identified groups of cells that are confidently annotated as mitotic cells and endocycle cells following these criteria: Mitotic cycle cells should have a positive z-score mean for mitotic cycle markers and a negative z-score mean for endocycle markers. Additionally, the mitotic cycle cells should have a positive z-score mean for 2C ploidy markers and a negative z-score mean for 4C, 8C, and 16C markers. The logic for endocycle cells is the exact opposite of that for mitotic cycle cells. Next, we used the confidently annotated cells as a reference and calculated the correlation of each cell's transcriptomic profile to the reference profiles, and annotated all the cells by comparing these correlations.

QUANTIFICATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

GraphPad Prism v.9 software was used to perform statistical tests. A two-tailed paired t-test analysis was used to determine the significant difference for binary comparisons in [Figures 4D](#) and [4J](#). A two-tailed Student's unpaired t-test was used to determine the significant difference for binary comparisons in [Figures 5E](#), [6D](#), [6E](#), [6G](#), [6H](#), [7F](#), and [S7H](#)). The significant differences between the samples were determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's multiple comparison tests in [Figures 5D](#), [7H](#), [S5O](#), [S5R](#), and [S5S](#). In figures * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Supplemental figures

Figure S1. Validation of the scRNA-seq cell cycle reference, related to Figure 1

(A) Principal-component analysis (PCA) plot of scRNA-seq cell cycle reference colored by cell cycle position. The lower panel shows a cell density plot of the cell cycle reference with the inferred cell cycle position and phase.

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(B) Expression patterns of markers for cell cycle phases across pseudotime of the cell cycle reference.
(C) Long-term confocal imaging of PlaCC1 reporter line. Root epidermal cells are shown.
(D–F) Long-term confocal imaging of lines expressing mNeonGreen-NLS (mNG) under G1 (D), S (E), and G2/M (F) marker gene promoters. G1 phase (time between mitosis until the disappearance of CDT1a-CFP signal) was used as a reference point to estimate in which cell cycle phase reporter lines display increased expression. Root epidermal cells are shown.
Single z sections are shown (C–F). Scale bars, 5 μm .

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Figure S2. Brassinosteroid-regulated gene expression fluctuations predominantly occur in mitotic cells, related to Figure 1

- (A) Expression patterns for representative brassinosteroid-related genes in proliferation domain atrichoblasts of the WT cell cycle reference.
- (B) Heatmap showing gene expression patterns of the 294 genes from (C) over cell cycle pseudotime in proliferation domain atrichoblasts in the brassinosteroid time course.
- (C) Analysis of published scRNA-seq data²⁵ reveals that the 294 brassinosteroid-induced BES1 and BZR1 target genes in G1-Module 2 respond to brassinolide (BL) treatment. The line represents the gene expression signature at each time point of brassinazole (BRZ) or BL treatment, calculated by summing Z scores for the 294 genes in proliferation domain atrichoblasts, truncated to $[-5,5]$.
- (D) Expression patterns of core cell cycle genes in proliferation domain atrichoblasts across pseudotime of the cell cycle reference upon brassinazole or BL treatment at different time points.
- (E) PCA showing 6,516 mitotic and 1,599 endocycle cells from proliferation domain atrichoblast scRNA-seq.
- (F) Z score mean of 2C, 4C, 8C, and 16C ploidy markers.
- (G) Normalized expression level of endocycle markers *SIM*, *SMR1*, and *CDC6*.
- (H) Normalized expression level of mitotic markers *KNOLLE*, *CSLD5*, and *HINKEL*.
- (I) Smoothed Z score sum of 294 brassinosteroid-induced genes in G1-Module 2 for endocycle and mitotic cycle cells.

Figure S3. Dynamics of brassinosteroid-related signaling components during cell division, related to Figure 2

(A) Long-term confocal imaging of roots co-expressing *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* and plasma membrane (PM) marker *pUBQ10:RCI2A:tdTomato*. Root epidermal cells are shown.

(B and C) Long-term confocal imaging of *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP* transgenic line. BZR1-YFP nuclear accumulation increases following cell division. Root cortical (B) and phloem (C) cells are shown.

(D) Time series analysis of a root epidermal cell during mitosis expressing *pUBQ10:BES1-Ypet*, *pUBQ10:H2B-mCherry*, and a *pCDT1a:CDT1a-CFP* G1 reporter.

(E) Quantification of BES1-Ypet and CDT1a-CFP signals ratios versus H2B-mCherry reference in the nucleus, before and after cell divisions (shown in D). Shades around lines represent a 95% confidence interval. a.u., arbitrary unit.

(F) Time series analysis of a root epidermal cell expressing ATSK11-GFP and ATSK22-GFP under the control of their native promoters during cell division. Root epidermal cells are shown. Several minutes before cell division, a strong ATSKs fluorescent signal is detected in the nucleus. As mitosis progresses, the nuclear signal becomes diffuse but sharply increases with the formation of the new daughter nuclei. At the end of mitosis, prior to cytokinesis, the nuclear signal disappears, and ATSKs re-localize to cytoplasm and PM.

Single z sections are shown (A–D and F). Scale bars, 5 μ m.

Figure S4. Expression patterns of brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes during cell division, related to Figure 3

(A) Long-term confocal imaging of *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* transgenic line. DWF4-GFP accumulates preferentially in the lower daughter cells following cell division. Root epidermal cells are shown.

(B) Tracking of two consecutive cell divisions in *pDWF4:DWF4-GFP* root epidermal cells.

(C) A patchy accumulation pattern of DWF4-GFP is absent when the fusion protein is expressed under the control of an epidermis-specific *WEREWOLF* (*WER*) promoter.

(D) Accumulation pattern of CPD-GFP expressed under the control of its native promoter. Root edges are marked by dashed white lines.

(E) Accumulation pattern of GFP-BR6OX2 expressed under the control of its native promoter.

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(F) Long-term confocal imaging of *pWER:DWF4-GFP* transgenic line. DWF4-GFP accumulates similarly in the upper and lower daughter cells following cell division. Root epidermal cells are shown.

(G) Long-term confocal imaging of *pCPD:CPD-GFP* transgenic line. CPD-GFP accumulates to a higher extent in the lower daughter cell following cell division. Root procambium cells are shown.

(H) Long-term confocal imaging of *pBR6OX2:GFP-BR6OX2* transgenic line. GFP-BR6OX2 accumulates to a greater extent in the lower daughter cell following cell division. Root endodermal cells are shown.

(I) GFP signal accumulation along the longitudinal axis of roots of stably transformed tomato plants with *pSICPD:SICPD-GFP* construct. Bright field (BF).

(J) *pSICPD:SICPD-GFP* expression pattern in apical and basal tomato root meristem. Note the patchy expression pattern similar to brassinosteroid biosynthetic genes in *Arabidopsis*. Roots were stained with propidium iodide (PI).

(K) Quantification of nuclear YFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells following cell division in dual reporter line *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP/pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato* (shown in [Figure S3A](#)), $n = 48$.

(L) Quantification of nuclear/cytoplasmic YFP signal ratio in upper and lower daughter cells following cell division in dual reporter line *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP/pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato* (shown in [Figure S3A](#)), $n = 48$.

(M) Quantification of nuclear YFP signal ratio between upper and lower daughter cells following cell division. Time points with maximum difference in nuclear BZR1-YFP nuclear intensity were chosen for measurement (around 120 min after division). Epidermal cells from four *pBZR1:BZR1-YFP/pUBQ10:RCI2A-tdTomato* roots were analyzed (shown in [Figure S3A](#)).

(N) Inducible expression of BES1-D-mCherry (lower) suppresses the accumulation and patchy pattern of DWF4-GFP observed in the control line (upper). 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to a fresh medium containing 10 μ M estradiol for 24 h before imaging. Maximum intensity projections of root meristems are shown. Epidermal cells were analyzed (K–M). n , number of cell division events (K–M). Shades around lines represent 95% confidence interval (K and L). Single z sections (A–C, F, G, and J) and maximum intensity projections (D, E, H, I, and N) are shown. Scale bars, 5 μ m in (A), (B), and (F)–(H), 20 μ m in (C)–(E), 100 μ m in (I) and (J), and 10 μ m in (N).

Figure S5. Dynamics of brassinosteroid-related transcription factors, receptors, and kinases during cell division, related to Figure 3

(A) Long-term confocal imaging of *pBES1::BES1-GFP* transgenic lines. BES1-GFP nuclear accumulation increases following cell divisions and is more pronounced in the upper daughter cells. Root epidermal cells are shown.
 (B) Long-term confocal imaging of *p35S::BZR1-YFP* transgenic lines. Root epidermal cells are shown.
 (C) Long-term confocal imaging of *p35S::BES1-GFP* transgenic lines. Root epidermal cells are shown.
 (D) Long-term confocal imaging of *p35S::BZR1-YFP* transgenic lines treated with proteasome inhibitor MG132. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to fresh medium containing 50 μ M MG132, mounted immediately in chambers, and imaged overnight in a vertical microscopy setup. Root epidermal cells are shown.

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(E) Quantification of nuclear YFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells following cell division in *p35S:BZR1-YFP* line shown in (B), $n = 22$.

(F) Quantification of nuclear GFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells following cell division in *p35S: BES1-GFP* line shown in (C), $n = 18$.

(G) Quantification of nuclear YFP signal in upper and lower daughter cells following cell division in *p35S:BZR1-YFP* line treated with proteasome inhibitor MG132 shown in (D), $n = 24$.

(H and I) Long-term confocal imaging of *pTMO5:TMO5-3GFP* and *pLHW:LHW-YFP* transgenic lines. These BR signaling-unrelated transcription factors do not display unequal accumulation in the daughter cells after cell divisions. Root xylem (TMO5) and cortical (LHW) cells are shown.

(J) Long-term confocal imaging of *pBRI1:BRI1-mCitrine* transgenic line. No obvious difference in BRI1-mCitrine was observed between upper and lower cells following cell division. Root epidermal cells are shown.

(K) A phylogenetic tree of *Arabidopsis* ATSKs, adapted from Dong et al.⁹⁴

(L) Expression and localization of *Arabidopsis* ATSKs tagged with GFP under the control of their native promoters. Root epidermal cells are shown.

(M) Nuclear accumulation of ATSK32-GFP reflects the brassinosteroid signaling status of the cell. Treatment with the brassinosteroid biosynthesis inhibitor brassinazole increases ATSK32-GFP nuclear localization, while treatment with BL restricts nuclear entry, compared with the mock control (DMSO). Root epidermal cells are shown. Plants were treated with chemicals for 24 h.

(N) The root growth phenotype of *atsk31/atsk32* CRISPR mutant plants in response to bikinin treatment. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to an agar medium containing either DMSO (mock) or bikinin (70 μ M) for 4 days.

(O) Quantification of the primary root growth shown in (N).

(P) The patchy accumulation of DWF4-GFP enzyme remains in *atsk31/atsk32* CRISPR mutant root apical meristems. Upon bikinin treatment, DWF4-GFP accumulation is completely abolished in *atsk31/atsk32* CRISPR background but not in the control line. Maximum intensity projections of root meristems from (N) are shown.

(Q) Root apical meristems of roots shown in (N). Cell walls were stained with PI. Meristematic cortical cells are colored.

(R) Quantification of the cortical meristem cell number shown and highlighted in (Q). BIK, bikinin (70 μ M).

(S) Quantification of the cortical meristem cell length (first 25 cells of individual roots) is shown and highlighted in (Q). BIK, bikinin (70 μ M). For (O, R, and S), all individual data points are plotted, horizontal bars represent the means, and error bars indicate SD. Significant differences between the samples were determined by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison tests. n.s., not significant.

n , number of cell division events analyzed (F and G). Shades around lines represent 95% confidence interval (F and G). Single z sections (A–D, H–J, L, and M) and maximum intensity projections (P) are shown. Scale bars, 5 μ m in (A)–(D) and (H)–(J), 20 μ m in (L), (M), (P), and (Q), and 1 cm in (N).

Figure S6. OPS- and OPL2-dependent brassinosteroid signaling is prominent in phloem, related to Figures 4, 5, and 6

(A) Overexpression of *OPL2-mCherry* under the control of 35S promoter inhibits *DWF4-GFP* accumulation. A root meristem with variable *OPL2-mCherry* expression is shown. Regions lacking *OPL2-mCherry* expression can be used as internal control. Arrows indicate cell files with strong *OPL2-mCherry* expression that lack *DWF4-GFP* signal.

(B) Accumulation of OPS-GFP and OPL2-GFP after treatment with BL and brassinosteroid biosynthesis inhibitor brassinazole. Root phloem (OPS-GFP) and epidermal (OPL2-GFP) cells are shown. Plants were treated with chemicals for 24 h.

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(C) Expression trends for *OPS* and *OPL2* are shown across the developmental zones of the atrichoblasts at each time point in the brassinosteroid time course. Color bars indicate the scaled expression level in the atrichoblast cells. PD, proliferation domain; TD, transition domain; E, elongation; D, differentiation. Heatmaps were produced based on data from Nolan et al.²⁵

(D) Long-term confocal imaging of *pOPS:OPS-GFP* transgenic line. Due to the polarized localization of OPS-GFP, the upper daughter cell accumulates higher amounts of the protein immediately after cell division in comparison to the lower one. Root protophloem cells are shown.

(E) Long-term confocal imaging of *pOPS:OPL2-GFP* transgenic line. Due to the polarized localization of OPL2-GFP, the upper daughter cell accumulates higher amounts of the protein immediately after cell division in comparison to the lower one. Root protophloem cells are shown.

(F) UMAP representation of the 3,645 proliferation domain phloem cells derived from a phloem pole atlas.⁵³ Color indicates cell cycle progression.

(G) Gene modules (Mod) identified from the clustering of proliferation domain phloem cells and their correlation with cell cycle progression.

(H) Gene expression patterns for each module are shown in (G).

(I) The enrichment of brassinosteroid-regulated BES1 and BZR1 target genes shows a peak of brassinosteroid-induced gene expression early in the cell cycle in G1-Module 2 (G1-Mod2), whereas MYB3R4 target genes are enriched in G2-to-M-to-G1-Module 9 (G2/M/G1-Mod9). Color represents $-\log_{10}p$ values from the indicated overlaps calculated from Fisher's exact test by GeneOverlap. The number of genes in each intersection is indicated inside each box.

(J) GO terms associated with putative upper and lower daughter cells in G1 phase.

(K) Gene expression of brassinosteroid-responsive genes in the upper and lower cells from G1 phloem scRNA-seq data. Single z sections are shown (A, B, D, and E). Scale bars, 20 μm in (A) and (B) and 5 μm (D) and (E).

Figure S7. Inducible *OPS* and *OPL2* knockdown and experimental validation of computational modeling simulations, related to Figures 6 and 7

(A) Guide RNA (gRNA) target positions within *OPS* and *OPL2* genes.

(B) Inducible CRISPR knockout of *OPS* and *OPL2* in *pOPS:OPS-GFP* and *pOPL2:OPL2-GFP* backgrounds. The same *XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* construct was introduced in both backgrounds. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to a fresh medium containing 10 μ M estradiol and immediately mounted in chambers and imaged overnight in a vertical microscopy setup. After 20 h of induction, both *OPS-GFP* and *OPL2-GFP* fluorescent signals almost completely disappeared from root meristems. Maximum intensity projections of root meristems are shown.

(C) Long-term induction of *OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* causes phenotypic changes similar to the *ops/opl2* mutant. Seedlings were germinated on mock or medium containing 5 μ M estradiol and grown for 9 days.

(D) Protophloem cells in the control *pOPS:OPS-GFP* line divide rapidly, whereas induction of *XVE:OPS-OPL2-CRISPR* leads to cell cycle arrest. 5-day-old seedlings were transferred to a fresh medium containing 10 μ M estradiol for 1 h before the start of the imaging session. *OPS-GFP* signal loss coincides with *CAS9-RFP* signal appearance. GFP signal allowed the identification of protophloem cells, and the nuclear *Cas9-RFP* signal was used to track cells once the GFP signal disappeared.

(E) The region of the highest *OPS* expression overlaps with the most prominent nuclear accumulation domain of *BZR1* in the protophloem of the root meristem.

(F) A model for the coordination of brassinosteroid signaling and biosynthesis during the cell cycle. During interphase, basal levels of brassinosteroid signaling are required for cell growth and progression through the cell cycle. As the cell approaches division, brassinosteroid signaling levels decrease, reaching a minimum at the G2-to-M transition, when *ATSKs* enter the nucleus to phosphorylate and displace *BZR1* and *BES1* transcription factors to the cytoplasm. At this stage, *OPS* and *OPL2* (*OPLs*) begin to be expressed and accumulate at the apical membrane of the mother cell, subsequently localizing to the cell plate. Immediately after mitosis, *OPLs* predominantly accumulate in the upper cell. Additionally, the *OPL* pool from the cell plate likely migrates toward the apical PM domain, increasing *OPL* concentration in the cytoplasm of the upper daughter cell. Through interaction and potential degradation, *OPLs* reduce *ATSK32* nuclear localization and overall abundance, ensuring the rapid reestablishment of brassinosteroid signaling. Other brassinosteroid signaling-related molecular players, such as protein

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phosphatase 2A (PP2A), may contribute to this rapid reestablishment by dephosphorylating BZR1 and BES1. During the G1 phase, in the lower daughter cell, ATSK32 enters the nucleus to maintain low brassinosteroid signaling levels, facilitating brassinosteroid biosynthesis. Other ATSKs are likely involved in this process. Eventually, OPLs accumulate in the lower daughter cell as well, establishing optimal brassinosteroid signaling levels. The polar nature of the brassinosteroid signaling activator exploits intrinsic cell polarity to enable rapid signaling reestablishment while simultaneously allowing hormone biosynthesis to proceed.

(G) Expression of *PlaCC1* cell cycle marker in Col-0 and *bri1/bri1/bri3* triple mutant.

(H) Quantification of the cell cycle duration in Col-0 and *bri1/bri1/bri3* root epidermal cells. Individual data points are plotted, horizontal bars represent the means, and error bars indicate SD. *n*, number of cells analyzed. A two-tailed Student's unpaired t test analysis was used to determine the significant difference. Maximum intensity projections (B) and single z sections (D, E, and G) are shown. Scale bars, 20 μm in (B), (E), and (G), 1 cm in (C), and 5 μm in (D).